

1 **Supporting Information for**

2
3 Accelerating local extinction associated with very recent climate change.
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9 **This PDF file includes:**

10 Appendices S1–S4
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22 Appendix S1. Details on field surveys

23 We conducted field surveys of *Sceloporus jarrovi* on 18 mountain ranges in southeast Arizona in
 24 2013–2017 and 2021–2022. The Peloncillo Mountains also have *S. jarrovi* populations, bringing the
 25 total to 19 mountain ranges in southeastern Arizona with *S. jarrovi*. However, the Peloncillos were
 26 excluded in the 2013–2017 surveys (Wiens et al., 2019) because the relevant portions of these
 27 mountains (where *S. jarrovi* occurs) are mostly in New Mexico. Therefore, we could not do
 28 resurveys of the Peloncillos that were comparable to other ranges that were surveyed in 2013–2017.

29 Resurveys were mostly conducted from March to October (with a very few in November and
 30 February; Dataset S1). Transects were done along trails or roads (if possible) and otherwise along
 31 canyons, slopes, and ridges. If no individuals of *S. jarrovi* were found at the lowest survey site from
 32 the original transect (2013–2017), the transect was extended upslope. The species was found at
 33 higher elevations on the same transect in all mountain ranges except for one transect in the Mule
 34 Mountains (Mules-1). We also recorded the apparent absence of lizards at potentially suitable sites
 35 (i.e. rock outcrops in Madrean Evergreen Woodland, see all records in Dataset S1). Two people were
 36 present on most searches, but the two people always searched the same part of the transect at the
 37 same time. Therefore, we give the time spent searching these transects (Tables S2–S5), but not
 38 “person hours” (since the times given here could be considered equivalent to a single person
 39 searching). For each search, the start time was taken from when the first suitable rock outcrop
 40 without lizards was found (indicated as “0” in Dataset S1) or when a lizard was first found at that
 41 site (regardless of species). The end times for each search are based on the same criterion (lizards or
 42 rock outcrops without lizards). Therefore, the approximate time spent searching each site can be
 43 obtained from Dataset S1, and is described more explicitly below. The same individual (J.J.W.) was
 44 present on all of the initial surveys (2013–2017) and resurveys (2022–2023), which facilitated
 45 revisiting the same rock outcrops in 2021–2022 where *S. jarrovi* was found in the initial surveys.

46 For each lizard found, geographic coordinates, and elevation were recorded with a handheld GPS
 47 device (Garmin eTrex® 10). Species identifications were confirmed in the field by the same
 48 individual (J.J.W.) for both initial surveys and resurveys

49 The resurvey of each transect either confirmed the initial lower limits of *S. jarrovi* found on that
 50 transect or else found evidence for an elevational shift. If *S. jarrovi* was found at the same lowest-
 51 elevation site where it was found in the initial survey (or lower, see below), then the transect was not
 52 continued further nor resurveyed again. In cases when the resurvey suggested an upward shift in the
 53 lower elevational limit of *S. jarrovi*, the resurvey was repeated at least one more time to confirm this
 54 finding (median number of resurveys=3, range=2–6, $n=9$ mountain ranges with upward shifts; Table
 55 S2). These resurveys were conducted at least 10 days after the initial resurvey (mean number of days
 56 between successive resurveys=92.3, median=33 days, range=10–322, $n=21$; dates in Table S2).
 57 Thus, conditions were not identical to the initial resurvey. On a given survey, the lowest-elevation
 58 sets of sites were typically surveyed for 20 minutes or more each time (Tables S2–S3), or until *S.*
 59 *jarrovi* was found (Table S4). For analyses of the elevational shifts, we used the lowest elevation
 60 sighting among all these resurveys. We provide a narrative description of the evidence for the
 61 absence of *S. jarrovi* at the lowest-elevation sites for each of the 9 relevant mountain ranges at the
 62 end of this section, including a summary of the time at each survey. Searches for each location are
 63 summarized in Tables S2–S3 (for locations with local extinction),

64 Note that for the Mules, we performed two transects, one on the northern slopes (Mules-1) and
 65 one on the southern slopes (Mules-2) of a large valley. These two transects shared the same lowest-
 66 elevation sites (Guest Road), which were close to the valley floor. Therefore, for all analyses that
 67 focused on the lowest-edge populations, we included only this low-elevation population for the
 68 Mules, and not both transects. For the Mules-1 transect (Juniper Flats Road), the elevational shift
 69 was based on the difference between the initial lowest-elevation site with *S. jarrovi* (in 2014; Guest
 70 Road) and the highest site surveyed on that transect. The highest site surveyed was close to the
 71 maximum elevation present in the Mules (see below).

72 The initial survey data were generally based on surveys done in 2013–2015. However, for one
 73 transect in the Santa Rita Mountains (Madera Creek), the lowest elevation sighting of *S. jarrovi* was

74 in 2017, while collecting behavioral data (Wiens et al., 2019). We included this observation as
 75 within the transect. We revisited this site and surveyed the lower part of this transect three times
 76 without finding *S. jarrovi* in 2022.

77 Based on the calculated differences in elevation, some mountain ranges appeared to have
 78 populations which occurred at lower elevations than in the initial survey (Table S6). However, these
 79 apparent downward shifts were generally small with a mean of -13.72 ± 17.14 m ($n=9$ downward
 80 shifts, ranging from -1.52 m to -56.69 m). There are at least three possible explanations for these
 81 apparent downward shifts. First, some cases might be actual downward shifts in elevation between
 82 surveys. Second, lizards may have been missed at the lowest-elevation sites in the initial surveys in
 83 2013–2015. Note that the transects in 2013–2015 were often based on a single survey (but typically
 84 going both up and down, such that each site was visited twice). Third, there may be small errors in
 85 elevation measurements made using the GPS unit.

86 To address this third explanation, we compared elevations inferred from GPS to those from
 87 topographic data by plotting linear site distances in Google Earth and using the map Gaia Topo (©
 88 2022 Outside Interactive, Inc.) for all putative elevational shifts (both downward and upward). Note
 89 that this comparison does not necessarily mean that the GPS measurements are wrong and the
 90 topographic estimates are right, especially since the exact sites are not identical between surveys
 91 (there are also small differences in linear distances between the sites: hence the potential for an
 92 elevational shift). We instead found that this second approach sometimes inferred no downward shift
 93 in specific cases. In the case of the Galiuros and the Huachucas, the GPS data suggested a downward
 94 shift of -6.40 m and -14.02 m, respectively, but on the topographic map the elevational difference is
 95 <1 m in both cases. The revisited sites had a linear distance of 10 and 39 meters (m) from the site
 96 visited in the initial surveys. Hence, the apparent downward shifts may be measurement errors in
 97 elevation from the GPS unit. The relatively small downward shifts inferred from GPS data in the
 98 Chiricahuas (-6.10 m, linear distance 20 m), the Little Dragoons (-1.52 m, linear distance 11 m), and
 99 the Santa Ritas-3 (Gardner Canyon, -2.74 m, linear distance 70 m) might also be due to small
 100 inaccuracies in the GPS unit, since an assessment based on the topographic map showed no
 101 differences (<1 m) in elevation. In the case of the Dragoons, the apparent downward shift from GPS
 102 data (-17.37 m, GaiaTopo: -20 m) may be due to slight differences in the resurveyed site compared to
 103 the initial site (linear distance 436 m). Here, one *S. jarrovi* was also found closer (290 m linear
 104 distance) to the initial site but at a site 14.33 m higher in elevation. The remaining downward shifts
 105 were supported by both GaiaTopo and GPS, including those in the Perillas (GaiaTopo/GPS shift: -4/
 106 3.35 m, linear distance 70 m), the Dos Cabezas (-12/-15.24 m, linear distance 244 m) and the
 107 Patagonias (-60/-57 m, linear distance 586 m). These might be explained by actual downward shifts
 108 or because individuals at lower elevations were missed in the initial surveys.

109 We also checked the mountain ranges with upward shifts in the same way. The Whetstones
 110 appeared to have a slight positive shift (4.88 m) based on the GPS data, but plotted on a map the sites
 111 have a linear distance of 14 meters and the individual found in the resurvey appeared on the
 112 topographic map ~ 2 m lower than the lowest individual in the initial survey. Therefore, this slight
 113 shift may be measurement error. For all other mountain ranges with upward shifts, the visual
 114 topographic examination also showed an upward shift in elevation (estimated topographic-based
 115 shifts/GPS shifts are: Baboquivaris=150/145 m, Coyotes=25/16 m, Mules 1–2=400/415–418 m,
 116 Pinalenos=95/91 m, Santa Ritas 1-Madera Creek=130/134 m, Santa Ritas 2-Dutch John Springs
 117 Trail=330/310 m, Santa Teresas=8/5 m, Whetstones=-2/5 m, Winchesters=50/52 m).

118 Overall, there was a very high correlation between elevational shifts inferred from GPS and Gaia
 119 Topo ($r=0.993$, $n=21$ transects). Furthermore, there is no significant difference in the shifts inferred
 120 from each method ($p=0.366$, paired, two-tailed t-test), suggesting that there is no systematic bias
 121 causing them to give different elevations. For all analyses, we used the elevations inferred from the
 122 GPS unit, given that this is the typical practice in range-shift studies.

123 For the majority of transects (15/21), we included sites at least 7 m in elevation below the lowest
 124 elevation for *S. jarrovi* in the initial survey, and >70 m below for 11 of these 15 (Dataset S1;
 125 Baboquivaris: 428 m below; lowest site on transect=1408; lowest initial site for *S. jarrovi*=1836,

126 1408/1836; Canelo Hills: 9 m; 1658/1667; Coyotes: 222 m; 1367/1589; Galiuros: 129 m; 1525/1654;
 127 Mules 1 and 2: 9 m; 1738/1747 [near the bottom of a valley]; Patagonias: 80 m; 1603/1683; Perillas:
 128 271 m; 1562/1833; Pinalenos: 190 m; 1560/1750; Quinlans: 75 m; 1406/1481; Santa Ritas-1
 129 [Madera Creek]: 78 m; 1416/1494; Santa Ritas-3 [Gardner Canyon]: 241 m; 1579/1820; Santa
 130 Teresas: 7 m; 1572/1579; Whetstones: 399 m; 1688/2087; Winchesters: 243 m; 1634/1877).
 131 Therefore, we had the potential to record larger downward shifts than those observed.

132 The other six transects require some explanation. In the case of the Santa Ritas-2 transect (Dutch
 133 John Springs Trail), the resurvey began at the previous lowest elevation site for *S. jarrovii*, but we
 134 found a substantial upward shift on that transect (ruling out a downward shift). For the other five
 135 transects, we began our survey close to the lowest-elevation site for *S. jarrovii* because this site was
 136 a low-elevation site in a relatively flat area, such as the bottom of a canyon (Chiricahuas, Dos
 137 Cabezas, Dragoons, Huachucas, Little Dragons). In these cases, it would be difficult to go
 138 substantially lower in elevation without traveling some distance from the lowest *S. jarrovii* site.
 139 Furthermore, in these cases, substantially lower elevations were generally lacking suitable habitat
 140 (i.e. rock outcrops in Madrean Evergreen Woodland). Therefore, surveying at even lower elevations
 141 near these transects was unlikely to yield a substantial downward shift. Even if a substantial
 142 downward shift had occurred on one or more of these five transects (despite being physically
 143 impossible in most cases) this would only impact our estimates of mean range shifts, and not the
 144 upward shifts that occurred in the other mountain ranges. For the sixth (Santa Ritas-2), our results
 145 showed an extensive upward shift (not a downward shift). Overall, possible downward shifts were
 146 unlikely to be strongly underestimated, and downward shifts would not impact the estimates of
 147 upward shifts if they were underestimated.
 148

149 **Inferring local extinction**

150 Upward shifts were apparently caused by extinction of low-elevation populations, and were inferred
 151 based on the inferred absence of *S. jarrovii* in low-elevation sites where it was previously found.
 152 This is the standard approach for estimating lowest-edge range shifts (e.g. Table S1), making our
 153 results directly comparable to these other studies. Therefore, we did not focus on changes in
 154 abundance or detection probabilities. Nevertheless, *S. jarrovii* could hypothetically be present in
 155 some surveyed sites but missed due to low abundance or other factors. However, we often observed
 156 *S. jarrovii* at higher elevations on the same transect on the same day that absences were recorded (or
 157 in other mountain ranges; 21/32 surveys; details in Table S2). Further, we typically documented
 158 lizard species of the same genus or family on these transects on the same day (*Sceloporus clarkii*,
 159 *Urosaurus ornatus*), even if no *S. jarrovii* were found that day (for 9 of the 11 days on which no *S.*
 160 *jarrovii* were found; Table S2; Dataset S1). Thus, absences were generally unlikely to be explained
 161 by suboptimal conditions for *Sceloporus* or other phrynosomatid lizards on a given day (Table S2).
 162 We observed no changes in habitat (e.g. deforestation, mining, road construction, wildfires) at these
 163 absence sites between surveys, suggesting that absences were not due to non-climatic factors. This
 164 species is territorial with limited home-range sizes (Simon, 1975; Ruby, 1978) and was almost
 165 always found on isolated rock outcrops (rather than dispersing between rock outcrops). Therefore,
 166 consistent absences at a given site seem to be explained by local extinction and not dispersal of
 167 individuals. Conversely, dispersing individuals might be found in locations that could not sustain
 168 populations. However, such occurrences seem unlikely to explain the overall patterns found here.
 169 Furthermore, we found neonates in 2022 at the lowest-elevation site in the region (Dos Cabezas),
 170 indicating that this surprisingly persistent population is viable. We also found that a low-elevation
 171 congener (*Sceloporus clarkii*) seems to have moved upwards to occupy low-elevation sites
 172 previously occupied by *S. jarrovii* on almost all transects where range contractions were inferred
 173 (8/9), and all those where the upward range shift in *S. jarrovii* was >52 meters (see Results).
 174 Previous analyses suggest that this congener is excluded from higher elevations by *S. jarrovii* (Wiens
 175 et al., 2019), further supporting the idea that *S. jarrovii* is indeed absent at these sites. Our statistical
 176 analyses of climate change and genetic variation show that both variables help predict which
 177 populations went extinct and which persisted (see Results). These non-random results provide

178 further evidence against the idea that the apparent local extinctions of *S. jarrovii* are simply
 179 stochastic artifacts of failing to observe this species at some low-elevation sites.
 180 Importantly, for the 12 transects where *S. jarrovii* remained extant at the lowest-elevation sites, it
 181 was found on the first visit for 9 transects, and on the second for the other 3 (Table S4). For the 17
 182 sites where genetic samples were obtained (Table S5), the species was found on the first visit for 15
 183 and on the second for the other two. Thus, among these 29 sites where *S. jarrovii* was present, a
 184 single visit was sufficient to find the species (83%; 24/29) or two was (17%; 5/29). For sites where
 185 local extinction was inferred, most were visited three or more times (78%). There were no lowest-
 186 elevation sites where the species was found only after three or more visits. Furthermore, on a given
 187 survey when the species was found, it was typically found after only 12 minutes (mean from lowest-
 188 elevation sites; Table S4) or 5 minutes (mean from genetic sites; Table S5). Conversely, the total
 189 average time spent searching at sites and transects with inferred warm-edge absences (summed
 190 across visits for that transect; Table S3) was 3:43 hours. However, finding *S. jarrovii* at new sites at
 191 higher elevations sometimes required more visits and more time than finding them again at
 192 previously recorded sites (Table S2). It seems highly unlikely that changes in behavior in the ~7
 193 years between surveys explained their apparent absence at many sites. For example, if lizards had
 194 switched to different microhabitats at some sites (e.g. from rocks to ground, from sun to shade) we
 195 would have observed this, since we observed other lizard species in other microhabitats on these
 196 transects (Dataset S1). We saw no signs of such changes in the extant populations. It is true that if *S.*
 197 *jarrovii* at low-elevation sites had switched from being diurnal to completely nocturnal in the past ~7
 198 years, then we would not have observed them at low-elevation sites (we only searched by day).
 199 However, this seems extremely unlikely, since (to our knowledge) all phrynosomatid species are
 200 diurnal (e.g. Anderson & Wiens, 2017). Thus, they appear to have maintained diurnal activity for
 201 >50 million years despite occurring over a range of different climates (i.e. there is no precedent for
 202 such dramatic changes in diel activity in this group, even over tens of millions of years). Further, the
 203 major clade to which phrynosomatids belong (Iguania) has maintained diurnal activity for ~150
 204 million years (Anderson & Wiens, 2017). Therefore, it seems especially unlikely that *S. jarrovii* at
 205 the low-elevation sites would switch to being completely nocturnal whereas conspecific lizards at
 206 nearby high-elevation sites remained diurnal. Overall, given these various lines of evidence, we
 207 considered there to be local extinctions at these sites. Finally, note that if we are wrong about local
 208 extinction in the Coyotes, Quinlans, or Winchesters, this would have limited impact on our main
 209 inferences, given the relatively small upward shifts in these mountain ranges (Fig. 1).

210 We note that a previous study also inferred local extinction in some montane *Sceloporus*
 211 populations (Sinervo et al., 2010). Those authors emphasized that *Sceloporus* are conspicuous, such
 212 that inferring erroneous extinction events is unlikely. They also considered upward range shifts by
 213 putative lowland competitors to support inferences of local extinction, as we do here. They stated
 214 that they quadrupled sampling effort (hours x personnel) relative to the initial surveys, but generally
 215 provided no information on the sampling effort for the initial surveys or resurveys (e.g. person hours,
 216 dates, times, number of visits). They did not focus specifically on warm-edge range limits, as we do
 217 here. Because they provided no specific information on when surveys and resurveys were done at
 218 individual sites, it is difficult to infer a time frame for local extinction from that study. We
 219 emphasize that based on our observations here, when *S. jarrovii* was present at a site, it was
 220 generally found on the first visit and after only ~8 minutes of searching (on average; 29 locations in
 221 Tables S4 and S5). For a minority of locations, a second visit was necessary (17%). Our observations
 222 suggest that a second visit to a site on a second day was potentially more important than the amount
 223 of time spent searching on a given visit. For example, for the five unsuccessful first visits to
 224 locations where *S. jarrovii* was eventually found, the failed searches were for 50 minutes (on
 225 average), whereas on the second visit it was found after only 11 minutes (on average; Tables S4 and
 226 S5).

227 Our results are based on distributional, climatic, and genetic data from sites that were surveyed
 228 and resurveyed over time, not every canyon and mountain slope in all 18 mountain ranges. Similarly,
 229 we focused only on the northwestern edge of the species' overall geographic range (Uetz &

230 Hallerman, 2022). Our goal was to document responses on these transects over time. New transects
 231 in other locations would not allow us to address this.

232 Finally, we acknowledge that we have not resolved the mechanisms that underlie local extinction
 233 in this system. This weakness is shared with most other resurvey studies that have focused on
 234 documenting range shifts from climate change (e.g. Table S1). Resolving those mechanisms would
 235 require a new, dedicated study, and is somewhat outside the major questions being asked here. It is
 236 important to note that *S. jarrovii* behaviorally thermoregulate and so a simple relationship involving
 237 increases in maximum climatic temperatures beyond their thermal tolerance limits is not expected
 238 (e.g. Beuchat, 1986). Analyses of low-elevation populations from 10 different mountain ranges in
 239 the region in 2016 suggest that their voluntary thermal maxima are generally very similar (~39°C)
 240 across a range of different climatic temperatures (Wiens et al., 2019). Thus, these lizards actively
 241 avoid temperatures that are too hot, and they do so before reaching temperatures at which they can
 242 no longer locomote (critical thermal maxima). As suggested previously based on niche modeling
 243 (Wiens et al., 2019), lower-elevation limits may be set by warm temperatures in winter. Populations
 244 may be susceptible to increasing temperatures in winter and spring, when live-bearing females brood
 245 their embryos (Beuchat, 1986; Beuchat & Ellner, 1987; Beuchat, 1989; see below). Interestingly, we
 246 found neonates in various populations during our fieldwork in the summer of 2022 (Chiricahuas,
 247 Dos Cabezas, Huachucas, Patagonias; Dataset S1), whereas the lack of neonates in the surviving
 248 high-elevation populations in the Mules (Mount Ballard) in the fall of 2022 was noticeable
 249 (especially given that neonates of *S. clarkii* were abundant on the same transect). The populations in
 250 the Mules experienced the most dramatic local extinctions (Fig. 1).

251 The idea that the lowest elevational range limits of *S. jarrovii* are set by the increasing exposure
 252 of brooding females to high temperatures at low elevations was proposed by Beuchat (1986).
 253 Beuchat (1986) documented that pregnant females maintain lower mean body temperatures than
 254 males or non-pregnant females in the wild. Further, Beuchat & Ellner (1987) predicted that pregnant
 255 females exposed to high temperatures would suffer from increased embryo mortality, whereas
 256 Beuchat (1988) showed experimentally that pregnant females that could not thermoregulate and were
 257 kept at warmer temperatures had significantly more dead or abnormal offspring than pregnant
 258 females kept at lower temperatures.

259

260 **Descriptions of individual mountain ranges with inferred local extinction**

261 Below, we describe our searches for *S. jarrovii* for those transects where there was an upward warm-
 262 edge range shift. Similar information is given subsequently for transects without upward range shifts.
 263 We give the dates and approximate time spent searching for each transect. Note that we do not give
 264 “person hours.” Even though two people were generally present on each survey, the two people were
 265 searching the same part of the transect at the same time.

266

267 **Baboquivaris.** *Sceloporus jarrovii* was found at several nearby sites in a small area of upper
 268 Thomas Canyon in 2015. On April 2, 2022, we resurveyed those sites for approximately 40 minutes
 269 (12:05–12:47; elevations 1842–1874 m) without finding *S. jarrovii* on our way up the transect. We
 270 found no *S. jarrovii* at higher elevations (up to 2470 m) but did on 29 April 2022, see below. We did
 271 find one *Sceloporus* of questionable identification, which was either *S. clarkii* or *S. jarrovii* (which
 272 disappeared before obtaining a positive identification). We also checked the low-elevation area of
 273 2015 sites again on our way back down (after ~1 hour at higher elevations), around 14:14, but did
 274 not count this as a separate search. We found *S. clarkii* at both lower and higher elevation sites that
 275 same day, indicating that conditions were suitable for *Sceloporus* in general. We resurveyed this
 276 transect on 29 April 2022. On our way up the transect, we revisited the sites with *S. jarrovii* from
 277 2015, searching for approximately 30 minutes (10:00–10:30; 1848–1876 m; two people). We found
 278 no *S. jarrovii*, but we found *S. clarkii* present at this site (and at higher elevations), further
 279 suggesting that *S. jarrovii* was absent there. We then found *S. jarrovii* at higher elevations on this
 280 transect approximately 1 hour later (1967–1981 m), confirming that conditions on 29 April 2022
 281 were suitable for *S. jarrovii*. On our way back down (~1:45 after the first search), we then

282 resurveyed the low-elevation site from 2015 once again, searching for approximately 30 minutes
 283 (12:16–12:48; 1864–1875 m; two people). Thus, the absence of *S. jarrovii* at the lowest-elevation
 284 site from 2015 was confirmed by three different searches over two days, and was further confirmed
 285 by the presence of *S. clarkii* at that site (and at higher elevations). Note that this location is relatively
 286 remote and requires a ~90-minute hike to reach the 2015 site with *S. jarrovii* (not accessible by
 287 road). However, there is a trail, which facilitated repeating the transect from 2015. Overall, this small
 288 area of Upper Thomas Canyon was resurveyed for approximately 1:40 hours by two people over two
 289 trips (with three searches total). Both trips included elevations below the sites from 2015, and
 290 numerous lizards were found on the way to these higher-elevation sites where *S. jarrovii* was found
 291 previously.

292 **Coyotes.** The sites in this mountain range are extremely inaccessible, with no roads or trails, and
 293 with extremely steep slopes and cliffs. We revisited the small area of sites where *S. jarrovii* was
 294 found in 2015. We surveyed first on 25 March 2022. We searched the area where *S. jarrovii* was
 295 found in 2015 for approximately 40 minutes (14:03–14:45; 1584–1598 m; two people). We found no
 296 *S. jarrovii*, but did find *S. clarkii* at the same rock outcrops where *S. jarrovii* was found in 2015,
 297 strongly suggesting that *S. jarrovii* was absent. We found *S. jarrovii* on the same day in the
 298 Quinlans. We revisited the sites again on 23 April 2022 and searched there on our way up the
 299 mountain slope for approximately 40 minutes (11:02–11:42; 1569–1600 m). Again, we found only *S.*
 300 *clarkii* present at the sites where *S. jarrovii* was present in 2015. We did find *S. jarrovii* present at
 301 higher elevations on this trip (1605–1615 m), confirming that conditions were suitable for *S. jarrovii*
 302 that day. After approximately 40 minutes at higher elevations, we searched on our way back down,
 303 for approximately 33 minutes (12:26–12:59; 1605–1540 m; two people) but we did not include this
 304 time in the totals for this transect, since the sites were slightly north of the previously known
 305 localities for *S. jarrovii* on this transect. In summary, based on two surveys, we found *S. jarrovii* to
 306 be absent at the lowest elevation sites where it was found in 2015, and we found *S. clarkii* to be
 307 present there instead. Note that our surveys on this mountain range primarily consisted of revisiting
 308 the lowest-elevation sites where *S. jarrovii* occurred previously (and nearby locations). We did not
 309 follow the same linear transect from lower elevations to these sites on each survey and resurvey,
 310 given the absence of roads and trails and the extreme difficulty and hazards associated with sampling
 311 in this mountain range. However, both trips included areas below the lowest elevations where *S.*
 312 *jarrovii* was found previously, and numerous lizards (of other species) were found at lower
 313 elevations. Overall, the relevant sites were resurveyed for approximately 1:35 hours by two people
 314 over two trips.

315 **Mules.** We searched the lowest-elevation sites (Guest Road) where *S. jarrovii* was found in 2014
 316 on 8 May 2021 for approximately 53 minutes (15:20–16:17; 1750–1810 m; two people). We found
 317 no lizards. We did find *S. jarrovii* on the same day in the Canelo Hills and Huachucas. We searched
 318 again on 7 August 2021, again for approximately 54 minutes (9:30–10:26; 1754–1818 m; two
 319 people) and again found no lizards. We searched these sites once more on 25 June 2022, for
 320 approximately 49 minutes (9:18–10:07; 1752–1819 m; two people). This time we found *S. clarkii* at
 321 1756 m, above the lowest elevation site where *S. jarrovii* was found in 2014 (1748 m), providing
 322 further support for the apparent absence of *S. jarrovii*. We also found *S. jarrovii* the same day in the
 323 Chiricahuas. Overall, this set of sites was resurveyed for approximately 2:36 by two people over
 324 three trips. We also observed *S. clarkii* at lower elevations below these sites (1732 m).

325 We surveyed higher elevation sites in the Mules along two transects. It was not possible to
 326 survey at higher elevations immediately above the low-elevation sites, because this was private
 327 property and inaccessible. Therefore, we first surveyed high-elevation historical sites to the north of
 328 the low-elevation site. We then repeatedly surveyed a transect that was south of the low-elevation
 329 sites, along a trail that spanned from low to high elevations.

330 In the spring and summer of 2022, we surveyed historical sites for *S. jarrovii* that are among the
 331 highest elevations in the Mules, near the radio/TV towers on Juniper Flats Road (Mules 1). There is
 332 a historical site for *S. jarrovii* 0.3 miles (483 meters) north of the TV tower from 1972 (UAZ 35115;

333 no elevation given). We surveyed sites north of these towers on 2 October 2021 for approximately
 334 33 minutes (15:40–16:13; 2149–2163 m; two people), finding only the lizard *Urosaurus ornatus*. On
 335 19 March 2022 we searched there again for ~20 minutes (15:02–15:22; 2153–2161 m; two people),
 336 finding no lizards. However, we found *S. jarrovii* on the same day in the Whetstones. On 25 June
 337 2022, we searched there for a third time, for ~34 minutes (10:41–11:15; 2147–2160 m), finding 5 *U.*
 338 *ornatus*. We found 15 *S. jarrovii* later the same day in the Chiricahuas at a similar elevation, strongly
 339 suggesting that conditions that day were appropriate for *S. jarrovii*. The highest sites surveyed on
 340 these transects (2163 meters) were close in elevation to the highest elevation possible in the Mules
 341 (Fissure Peak; 2248 meters, but which lacks previous records for *S. jarrovii*). Our analyses of range
 342 shifts for this transect treated the highest elevation surveyed here (2163 meters) as if this was the
 343 new lowest elevational limit for the species on this transect. By focusing on these sites on Juniper
 344 Flats Road, we documented the absence of the species from the high-elevation area where it was
 345 known to have occurred previously. These sites were collectively resurveyed for approximately 87
 346 minutes (1:17 hours) by two people over three trips.

347 We also searched a historical site that was 0.3 miles (483 meters) east of the radio towers, which
 348 was slightly lower in elevation (from 1972; UAZ 37973; 2084 meters elevation; two people). We
 349 searched there for ~20 minutes (16:30–16:50; 2048–2059 m; two people) on 2 October 2021, finding
 350 a *S. clarkii* there (also suggesting the absence of *S. jarrovii*). We searched there again for ~20
 351 minutes (15:37–15:58; 2037–2070 m; two people) on 19 March 2022, finding no lizards. Again, we
 352 found *S. jarrovii* in the nearby Whetstone Mountains earlier that same day, strongly suggesting that
 353 conditions were appropriate that day for *S. jarrovii*. In total, these sites were resurveyed for ~40
 354 minutes by two people over two trips. We did not include this site in the total times for the Mules-1
 355 transect, however. We instead focused primarily on surveying the highest-elevation sites.

356 We treated these higher elevation sites in the Mules as if *S. jarrovii* went locally extinct there
 357 during the same time frame as the lower-elevation sites. However, since we did not survey these sites
 358 until 2021–2022, it is possible that they instead went extinct at these sites before 2014. Although this
 359 is possible, it would require that populations at higher elevations were disappearing before those at
 360 lower elevations, which is inconsistent with the pattern observed in all the other transects with
 361 upward range shifts (and the general pattern observed in climate-change research). It should also be
 362 noted that for all range shifts, we do not know exactly when the populations went extinct, only that it
 363 happened within a certain window of time (e.g. after 2014, before 2021).

364 In the fall of 2022, we also surveyed a second transect in the Mules (Mules-2), south of the low-
 365 elevation site. This transect was added to address whether or not *S. jarrovii* was truly absent at the
 366 highest elevations in the Mules, as suggested by the results from the first transect (Mules-1). We
 367 utilized an established trail that extends from a parking lot at Mule Pass (off of North Old Divide
 368 Road) up to the top of Mount Ballard and then to Fissure Peak (the highest point in the Mules). This
 369 trail begins at ~1800 m elevation, above the highest-elevation localities on Guest Road. We surveyed
 370 first on 24 September 2022. We searched for ~4:05 hours along this transect (9:22–13:27; 1804–
 371 2244 m; two people). We found *S. clarkii* up to 1951 meters. We found an adult *S. jarrovii* at 2230
 372 meters and two adults at 2181 meters, all near the peak of Mount Ballard. We surveyed this transect
 373 again on 12 October 2022 for ~2:49 hours (11:57–14:46; 1833–2182 m; two people). We found a
 374 subadult *S. jarrovii* at 2182 meters and an adult at 2165 meters. One of us surveyed a third time on
 375 22 October 2022, for ~2:58 hours (13:30–16:28; 1841–2186 m; one person). We found no *S. jarrovii*
 376 at the sites at which they were found on the previous survey, but we found three *U. ornatus* and one
 377 *S. clarkii* at lower elevations. However, conditions were relatively cloudy, and this may have
 378 suppressed lizard activity overall. Importantly, we found no juvenile *S. jarrovii* on any of these three
 379 surveys, but we did find small juveniles of *S. clarkii*. These observations suggest that *S. jarrovii* may
 380 not have successfully reproduced along this transect in 2022, whereas *S. clarkii* did. Overall, this
 381 transect was surveyed by at least one person for ~9:52 hours over three trips.

382
 383 **Pinalenos.** In 2015, we searched for *S. jarrovii* at various sites along Swift Trail Road (State
 384 Route 366). The lowest *S. jarrovii* was found at 1750 meters, below Wet Creek Canyon. The highest

385 *S. clarkii* were found at 1578 meters. This is a small canyon adjacent to the highway, with a small
 386 area to search. On 3 April 2021 we redid this transect. One person searched the same lowest
 387 elevation site for *S. jarrovii* for 13 minutes (15:33–15:46; ~1760 m), but found no lizards.
 388 Nevertheless, in a nearby site above this one (~15 minutes earlier) we found four *S. jarrovii* over the
 389 course of 4 minutes, clearly showing that conditions were appropriate that afternoon for *S. jarrovii*.
 390 On 28 August 2021 we revisited these two sites again. Again, we found *S. jarrovii* present at the
 391 upper elevation site, but absent at the lower-elevation site, after searching that low-elevation site for
 392 20 minutes (near 16:35; ~1749 m; one person). However, this time we found *S. clarkii* present at the
 393 lower elevation site, further suggesting the absence of *S. jarrovii* at that site. Finally, we visited this
 394 site a third time on 5 June 2022. We searched for 20 minutes (16:21–16:41; ~1751–1769 m; two
 395 people), finding no lizards. However, we found *S. jarrovii* at a nearby higher-elevation site roughly
 396 30 minutes earlier, again suggest that conditions were appropriate that day for *S. jarrovii*. Overall,
 397 this single, small low-elevation site was searched by one or two people for a total of ~53 minutes
 398 over three trips.

399 **Quinlans.** In 2013, we found *S. jarrovii* along the road to Kitt Peak on the north slope of the
 400 mountain range, at an elevation of 1481 meters. In 2013, the maximum elevation where we found *S.*
 401 *clarkii* along this section of the road was 1416 meters. On 27 March 2022 we revisited these sites.
 402 We searched for ~50 minutes (11:08–11:58; 1406–1495 m; two people) and the lowest elevation
 403 where we found *S. jarrovii* was 1495 meters (same canyon, but at a slightly higher elevation). The
 404 highest elevation where we found *S. clarkii* was 1477 meters, effectively the same elevation where *S.*
 405 *jarrovii* occurred in 2013. On 23 April 2022 we revisited these sites again, searching for ~35 minutes
 406 (16:51–17:26; 1471–1504 m). We again found *S. jarrovii* absent at the highest-elevation site from
 407 2013. We found *S. clarkii* at 1472 meters, and we found *S. jarrovii* on the same day in the nearby
 408 Coyotes. We revisited this canyon a third time on 26 May 2022 and searched for ~35 minutes (9:28–
 409 10:03; 1477–1497; two people). Again, we found *S. jarrovii* absent at the lowest-elevation site from
 410 2013, but present at a higher-elevation site (1497 meters). In summary, we confirmed the small
 411 upward shift in *S. jarrovii* in this canyon based on 3 surveys, and one of these surveys suggested that
 412 *S. clarkii* now occurs at the lowest-elevation site previously occupied by *S. jarrovii* (much higher
 413 than the highest record for *S. clarkii* in 2013). Overall, this small area was searched by two people
 414 for a total of ~120 minutes (two hours) over three trips.

415 **Santa Ritas 1. Madera Creek.** We conducted transects in three locations the Santa Ritas. Two
 416 were on the west side, both in Madera Canyon. The third was on the east side (Gardner Canyon).
 417 Madera Canyon runs north to south. One transect was along Madera Creek, and thus also runs north-
 418 south. In 2013, the lowest elevation for *S. jarrovii* along Madera Creek was along the Amphitheatre
 419 Nature Trail at 1525 m. In 2015, the highest elevation for *S. clarkii* there was also at the
 420 Amphitheatre Nature Trail, at 1586 m. However, in 2017, *S. jarrovii* was recorded at a lower
 421 elevation along Madera Creek, at 1494 meters. We surveyed along Madera Creek six times in 2021–
 422 2022, including 15 May 2021 (~50 minutes; 17:55–18:45; two people), 31 May 2021 (~1 hour, 45
 423 minutes; 9:50–11:35), 11 October 2021 (~52 minutes; 10:59–11:51; one person), 30 April 2022 (~1
 424 hour, 28 minutes; 12:28–13:56; two people), 2 June 2022 (~1 hour, 52 minutes; 8:47–10:39; two
 425 people), and 30 October 2022 (~1 hour, 20 minutes; 14:29–15:49; two people). On 15 May 2021, we
 426 surveyed from 1518 to 1537 meters, but no *S. jarrovii* or *S. clarkii* were found. On 31 May 2021, we
 427 surveyed from 1530 meters to 1686 meters, and found *S. jarrovii* at 1648 meters at the lowest and *S.*
 428 *clarkii* at 1658 at the highest (indicating some overlap). On 11 October 2021, we surveyed from
 429 1565 to 1675 meters, and found *S. jarrovii* at 1628 meters and *S. clarkii* at 1647 meters. Note that on
 430 3 April 2022, we also visited Madera Creek, but primarily at higher elevations (1647–1695 m), and
 431 we did not include this in the totals. On 30 April 2022, we surveyed from 1465 meters to 1648
 432 meters, and found no *S. jarrovii*, but found *S. clarkii* at 1648 meters. We did find *S. jarrovii* on the
 433 same day in two other locations in the Santa Ritas (Gardner Canyon and Mount Hopkins Road). On
 434 2 June 2022, we surveyed from 1474 to 1667 meters, but found no *S. jarrovii*. On 30 October 2022,
 435 we surveyed from 1417 to 1515 meters, and found *S. clarkii* at 1417 meters but no *S. jarrovii*. In

436 summary, a total of six surveys suggest that *S. jarrovii* no longer occurs below 1628 meters along
 437 Madera Creek, despite occurring at 1494 meters in 2017. Furthermore, we found that *S. clarkii* now
 438 occurs up to 1658 meters, despite having been found only up to 1586 meters in 2015. Overall, this
 439 transect was resurveyed by at least one person for a total of ~8:07 hours over six trips.

440 **Santa Ritas 2. Dutch John Spring Trail.** The other transect in Madera Canyon was along
 441 Dutch John Springs Trail, beginning at Bog Springs Campground. This transect begins well above
 442 Madera Creek and runs approximately east-west, going up the west-facing slope of Madera Canyon.
 443 In 2013, *S. jarrovii* was found at the Dutch John Springs Trail trailhead, at the highest elevation in
 444 Bog Springs Campground (1542 meters). In 2015, *S. clarkii* was found at elevations of 1494, 1527,
 445 and 1551 meters in Bog Springs Campground. On 11 October 2021, we surveyed along the Dutch
 446 John Springs Trail starting from the Bog Springs Campground for ~21 minutes (9:49–10:10; 1542–
 447 1671 m; two people). We found no *S. jarrovii*, but did find *S. clarkii* at 1568 meters. We surveyed up
 448 to 1671 meters. On 29 October 2021, we again surveyed the Dutch John Springs Trail, this time for
 449 ~2 hours, and extending up to 1779 meters (11:23–13:23; 1565–1779 m; but beginning at 1542 m;
 450 two people). We again found no *S. jarrovii* but found *S. clarkii* at 1687 meters. On 28 November
 451 2021, we surveyed the Dutch John Springs Trail again, this time for ~1 hour and 15 minutes (15:00–
 452 16:15; 1542–1838 m), going up to 1838 meters. Again, no *S. jarrovii* were found but *S. clarkii* was
 453 found at 1826 meters. On 3 April 2022, we surveyed the Dutch John Springs Trail for ~49 minutes
 454 (16:35–17:24; 1573–1852; two people). We found no *S. clarkii*, but found *S. jarrovii* at 1852 meters.
 455 In summary, we surveyed along the Dutch John Springs Trail a total of 4 times, each time starting at
 456 the Bog Springs Campground (1542 m), and confirmed the absence of *S. jarrovii* at lower elevations
 457 each time. We note that not every survey extended to the highest elevations, but the last three trips
 458 were all close to the highest elevations. Importantly, we found the highest-elevation *S. clarkii*
 459 occurring close to the lowest elevation *S. jarrovii* (1826 for *S. clarkii*, 1852 for *S. jarrovii*). This
 460 pattern further suggests that *S. jarrovii* no longer occurs at lower elevations on this transect. Overall,
 461 this transect was resurveyed by two people for ~4:25 hours over four trips.

462 **Winchesters.** In 2015, *S. jarrovii* was found as low as 1867 meters in the Winchesters, and *S.*
 463 *clarkii* was found as high as 1864. We resurveyed the Winchesters a total of 3 times. On 16 October
 464 2021, we surveyed for 1:54 hours (15:15–17:09; 1634–1916 m; two people), and found no *S.*
 465 *jarrovii*. On 15 March 2022, we surveyed again for 3:16 hours (15:08–17:24; 1666–1921 m; two
 466 people), and found no *S. jarrovii*. On 16 April 2022, we surveyed for a third time (for ~3:46 hours;
 467 9:18–13:04; 1625–1922 m; two people), and only found one *S. jarrovii*, and only at a somewhat
 468 higher elevation (1919 meters). Thus, three surveys confirmed the apparent absence of *S. jarrovii* at
 469 lower elevations. Note that we found one individual on 16 October 2021 that we tentatively
 470 identified as *S. clarkii* at 1916 meters, but it hid before a confident identification could be made (it
 471 was either *S. clarkii* or *S. jarrovii*). If this individual were considered *S. clarkii*, it would represent an
 472 upward range shift, and would help further confirm the loss of lower elevation populations of *S.*
 473 *jarrovii*. On the other hand, if it was instead *S. jarrovii*, it would have negligible impact on our
 474 results (i.e. 1916 m is almost the same as the lowest *S. jarrovii* at 1919 meters). Otherwise, we found
 475 no *S. clarkii* in our resurveys of this mountain range. Overall, this transect was resurveyed by two
 476 people for ~8:56 over three trips. The highest elevations (>1800 meters) specifically were surveyed
 477 for approximately 1:05 hours on 16 October 2021 (16:04–17:09; 1801–1916 m), 1:46 on 15 March
 478 2022 (15:38–17:24; 1895–1921 m), and 1:56 on 16 April (9:53–11:49; 1808–1922 m), for a total of
 479 ~287 minutes (~4:47 hours).

480

481 **Descriptions of individual mountain ranges with extant lowest-elevation populations**

482 Below, we describe our searches for *S. jarrovii* for those transects where there was no upward warm-
 483 edge range shift. We give the dates and approximate time spent searching for each transect, and
 484 especially the approximate time spent searching at the relevant location until *S. jarrovii* was found.

485 Note that we do not give “person hours.” Even though two people were generally present on each
 486 survey, the two people were searching the same part of the transect at the same time.
 487

488 **Canelo Hills.** The relevant area (Parker Canyon) was resurveyed on 8 May 2021. It is relatively
 489 close to the road, and there is only a small area where *Sceloporus jarrovi* was found previously.
 490 Two individuals were found within ~22 minutes (10:45–11:07; 1658–1672 m; two people), with the
 491 first found after ~19 minutes (10:45–11:04). This site is a relatively flat canyon bottom.

492 **Chiricahuas.** The lowest-elevation site (on the east side of the canyon bottom of Cave Creek,
 493 near the Visitor Center) was resurveyed on 5 June 2022. Five individuals (including two neonates) of
 494 *S. jarrovi* were found at or on the way to the lowest-elevation site, over ~34 minutes (9:07–9:41;
 495 1490–1502 m; three people). The species was found immediately upon reaching the lowest-elevation
 496 site. Because this site is near the bottom of the canyon, the survey went from low elevations to
 497 slightly lower elevations, but it would be difficult to go substantially lower because the canyon
 498 bottom is relatively flat and close to the valley floor at this point.

499 **Dos Cabezas.** The lowest-elevation site was revisited on 3 April 2021. Two individuals of *S.*
 500 *jarrovi* were found over 9 minutes (16:50–16:59; 1259–1279 m; two people), and the first was
 501 found upon arrival at the appropriate habitat.

502 **Dragoons.** This mountain range was first resurveyed on 10 April 2021. An individual of *S.*
 503 *jarrovi* at the lowest elevation was spotted from the car driving into the site (11:10; 1490 m; two
 504 people), before we could begin our resurvey, and another was spotted 12 minutes later (11:22; 1503
 505 m).

506 **Galiuros.** This mountain range was resurveyed on 20 February 2021. This is earlier in the year
 507 than all the other resurveys, and in our experience the species is less abundant in winter (and active
 508 only during the hottest part of the day, late afternoon). The previous lowest-elevation site for *S.*
 509 *jarrovi* was checked at ~14:00 hours for ~10 minutes (14:00–14:10; 1645–1657 m; one person) on
 510 the way up the mountain and then again on the way backdown at ~15:00. On the way back down,
 511 two individuals of *S. jarrovi* were found after ~19 minutes of searching at the low-elevation sites
 512 (14:58–15:17; 1648–1658 m; one person). The lowest was found after ~19 minutes (15:17). This
 513 survey also included lower-elevation sites below the recent lowest record for *S. jarrovi* (13:20–
 514 14:00; 1525–1645 m).

515 **Huachucas.** The previous lowest-elevation site (lower part of Scotia Canyon) was resurveyed on
 516 8 May 2021. An individual of *S. jarrovi* was found after ~16 minutes of searching (10:04–10:20;
 517 two people).

518 **Little Dragoons.** The lowest-elevation site was resurveyed on 30 May 2022. An individual of *S.*
 519 *jarrovi* was found (1776 m) after looking for ~23 minutes (7:43–8:06; 1775–1782 m; two people).

520 **Patagonias.** The transect on Duquesne Road on the east side of the crest was resurveyed on 20
 521 March 2021, for ~1 hour (16:25–17:25; 1600–1780 m; two people). Two individuals of *S. jarrovi*
 522 were found only at higher elevations (1769 and 1780 m). The transect was surveyed again on 20
 523 June 2021 for ~1 hour (9:02–9:55; 1576–1795 m; two people). The lower elevations (below 1700 m)
 524 were surveyed for ~28 minutes (9:27–9:55; 1576–1694 m) and the lowest-elevation individual was
 525 found after ~18 minutes (9:45; 1626 m). Two individuals were also found at higher elevations
 526 (>1700 m). A total of 3 individuals were found. Note that on 20 June 2021, the lower elevations
 527 were surveyed, then the higher elevations, and then the lowest elevations were surveyed on the way
 528 back down.

529 **Perillas.** The Perillas were resurveyed on 10 April 2022. The survey was conducted over ~2:32
 530 hours (9:35–12:07; 1562–1849 m; two people), but much of this time was spent hiking to and from

531 higher elevations (there is suitable habitat only near the peaks, with no roads or trails leading to
532 higher elevations). At higher elevations close to the lower-elevation limits (>1795 m) a total of three
533 individuals of *S. jarrovii* were found in ~28 minutes (10:27–10:55; 1797–1849 m), with the first
534 individuals found after ~12 minutes (10:27–10:39; 1797–1830 m).

535 **Santa Ritas 3 (Gardner Canyon).** This location was first resurveyed on 12 September 2021 for
536 ~52 minutes (10:36–11:28; 1808–1871 m; two people). Two individuals of *S. jarrovii* were found,
537 the lowest at an elevation of 1871 meters (higher than the previous lowest-elevation site on this
538 transect). The location was resurveyed again on 30 April 2022, for ~27 minutes (9:42–10:09; 1817–
539 1846 m; two people). An individual of *S. jarrovii* was found at an elevation of 1817 meters at the
540 beginning of the search of the previous lowest-elevation site. Note that we hiked to this site from
541 lower elevations prior to each search.

542 **Santa Teresas.** This location was first resurveyed on 3 April 2021. The area was searched for ~1
543 hour (10:50–11:50; 1572–1633 m; one person), but no individuals of *S. jarrovii* were found. The
544 location was resurveyed again on 15 August 2021 for ~45 minutes (16:27–11:12; 1585–1602 m; one
545 person), and an individual of *S. jarrovii* was found after ~11 minutes (16:38; 1586 m). Note that on
546 the second survey we initially went to the lowest part of the canyon (and found *S. jarrovii* present),
547 and so the survey went from low to lower elevations, and we did not resurvey higher elevations.

548 **Whetstones.** The location near Mine Canyon was resurveyed on 19 March 2022. Previously
549 (2014–2015), *S. jarrovii* was found only at the highest elevations. We resurveyed at elevations
550 >2,075 meters for approximately 69 minutes (10:38–11:47; 2077–2094 m; two people). We
551 encountered 3 individuals of *S. jarrovii*, the first after ~27 minutes (11:15). This survey also included
552 time at lower elevations (9:32–10:38; 1892–2077 m; 11:47–12:17; 2081–1913 m; 12:35–13:20;
553 1688–1737 m; all two people).

554

555 Appendix S2. Details on meta-analysis

556 We compared our estimates of upward range shifts at the lower elevational range edge of *Sceloporus*
557 *jarrovi* populations to published estimates of comparable range shifts in other organisms. We
558 utilized the published data assembled in the meta-analysis by Rumpf et al. (2019). We extracted start
559 and end dates of the survey periods from the 22 studies (Dataset S2). To calculate the time between
560 surveys, we subtracted the years between the first survey and the resurvey. For surveys that spanned
561 more than one year, midpoint values (means) of the initial and final years were used. The rates of
562 range change were then calculated by dividing the total shift in elevation by the time between
563 surveys.

564 We compiled data on upward shifts in the lowest elevational range limits for $n=1202$
565 observations from 1026 different species (i.e. some species had multiple range shift values due to
566 observations in different localities). The mean rate of species showing upward shifts was 5.39 m/year
567 (range=0.01–85 m/year, $n=648$ species with upward range contractions).

568 Two upward-shift values (i.e. rate of range contractions, 85 and 70 m/year) were found to be
569 higher than the highest value reported in our study (59.26 m/year in the Mules-1: Juniper Flats;
570 Table 1). These rates were from a study on reptiles and amphibians in the Tsaratanana Mountain in
571 Madagascar (Raxworthy et al., 2008). This study sampled amphibians and reptiles at three sites at
572 1600 m, 2050 m, and 2500 m. The first survey took place in 1993 and the resurvey in 2003. Note
573 that the range shifts (and associated rates) in that study might be overestimated because of the
574 relatively large differences in elevation (>400 m) between the three sites.

575 Another rate was found to be similar to the maximum rate in our study, from a study on
576 bumblebees in Spain (Ploquin et al., 2013). In the species *Bombus wurflenii* the authors reported a
577 lower edge upward shift of 59.08 m/year. The first sampling in this study took place in 1988–1989,
578 whereas the resurveys were in 2007–2009. Each site was visited once for 30 minutes. To analyze
579 extinction/colonization events, the sites in this study were grouped into 100-m intervals. Local
580 extinction was inferred when the species was not recorded within this interval in the second
581 sampling period. This approach is slightly different from ours. First, the shifts reported are not along
582 the same transect. Second, the shifts are not estimated between two specific elevational values but
583 within an elevational interval. Furthermore, it focuses on a flying insect, which may be more likely
584 to be transient in a given location than the highly territorial, rock-dwelling *Sceloporus jarrovi*.
585

586 Appendix S3. Details on historical records

587 We obtained historical records of *S. jarrovi* to determine if there were upward shifts in their lower
 588 elevational range limits prior to the initial surveys in 2013–2017. We searched for the lowest
 589 elevation records in the same 18 mountain ranges resurveyed in 2021–2022. To ensure comparability
 590 with our survey data, the only records used were from the same transects (i.e. same canyon and/or
 591 road) and with clear elevational information (Table S7). We did not estimate elevations based on
 592 distances by road. Data from museum collections were obtained by searching all geographically
 593 relevant records of *S. jarrovi* from the University of Arizona collection and VertNet
 594 (<http://vertnet.org/>). For VertNet we searched using the name of each mountain range as a keyword.

595 We also used results from a published paper on the distribution of reptiles in the Whetstone
 596 Mountains (Turner et al., 2003), a range which otherwise lacked museum records for *S. jarrovi*.
 597 Coordinates were converted to decimal numbers. If no exact coordinates were provided, we used
 598 descriptions of obvious locations (e.g. a picnic area or campground) and estimated the coordinates
 599 using Google Earth (Table S7). However, we only used historical records that provided specific
 600 values for elevations. We also recorded the date when the relevant specimens were collected. In the
 601 case of upward shifts, we note that our analyses do not address when exactly the species may have
 602 disappeared from a given low-elevation site. However, this is true for all of our estimates of range
 603 shifts, and for estimates of range shifts in other studies.

604 Historical records from museum specimens were not necessarily based on systematic surveys of
 605 elevational transects over time. However, they can be used to document the presence of *S. jarrovi* at
 606 lower elevations than those in the initial surveys (2013–2017). Furthermore, we also surveyed the
 607 specific sites associated with the relevant historical records and helped to further confirm the absence
 608 or presence of *S. jarrovi* at most of these sites in 2021–2022 (see below). Four mountain ranges
 609 lacked specific historical records (Baboquivaris, Coyotes, Dos Cabezas, Perillas). Three other
 610 mountain ranges (Huachucas, Mules, Patagonias) had historical records but had to be excluded
 611 because we could not find usable observations (i.e. with elevation values) on the same transects that
 612 were surveyed in 2013–2017.

613 The lowest historical records for each mountain range are given in Table S7. For 5 transects,
 614 there were no upward shifts between the historical period (ranging from year 1956–2005) and the
 615 lowest-edge elevation estimated in the surveys in 2013–2017 and we thus classified them as
 616 persistent for this historical interval (Chiricahuas, Dragoons, Santa Ritas-1: Madera Creek, Santa
 617 Ritas-2: Dutch John Trail, Santa Teresas; Table S7). We found upward shifts (i.e. local extinction at
 618 the lowest elevations) between the historical records and the initial surveys (2013–2017) on 7
 619 transects (total shift in m, shift rate in m per year): Canelo Hills (22.73 m, 2.27 m/year), Galiuros
 620 (204.45 m, 14.60 m/year), Pinalenos (134.55 m, 2.36 m/year), Quinlans (17.72 m, 0.35 m/year),
 621 Santa Ritas-3: Gardner Canyon (249.66 m, 5.31 m/year), Whetstones (386.27 m, 21.46 m/year), and
 622 Winchesters (196.9 m, 12.31 m/year). These elevational shifts are shown graphically in Fig. S1.

623 We also helped confirm the absence of *S. jarrovi* from most of these low-elevation historical
 624 sites in our 2021–2022 surveys (all but the Canelo Hills). Specifically, we surveyed for *S. jarrovi* at
 625 lower-elevation sites in (all with two people): the Galiuros (Deer Creek; 1525–1657 m; 20 Feb.
 626 2021; ~50 minutes; 13:20–14:10), Pinalenos (Noon Creek Campground and Round the Mountain
 627 Trail; 1560–1613 m; 3 April 2021; Noon Creek: 13:40–13:58 [38 minutes], Round the Mountain:
 628 14:19–14:59 [40 minutes]; total of ~78 minutes), Quinlans (road to Kitt Peak; 1406–1476; 27 March
 629 2022; ~50 minutes; 11:08–11:58), Santa Ritas-3 (road to Gardner Canyon; 1579 m; 12 September
 630 2021; ~23 minutes; 9:00–9:23), Whetstones (Mine Canyon: 1688–1737 m; 19 March 2022; ~35
 631 minutes; 12:45–13:20), and Winchesters (Warbonnet Ranch: 1634–1767 m; 16 October 2021; ~35
 632 minutes [15:15–15:50]; 1666–1750 m; 15 March 2022; ~34 minutes [14:08–14:42]; 1639–1777 m;
 633 16 April 2022; ~59 minutes [12:05–13:04]). We did not find *S. jarrovi* at lower elevations at these
 634 locations, although it was found at higher elevations on each transect (on at least one visit). We did
 635 not specifically survey the lower elevations of Parker Canyon in the Canelo Hills in 2021–2022, but
 636 our surveys in 2013–2017 found this species at only one higher-elevation location in the canyon
 637 bottom, as did our surveys in 2021.

638 We compared the upward shifts inferred between the historical records (1956–2005) and surveys
639 (2013–2017) to the upward shifts inferred from the surveys (2013–2017) and resurveys (2021–
640 2022). Specifically, we tested for an increase in the more recent shifts using a two-sample, one-tailed
641 t-test in R. We did not compare all the shifts between these two time periods because apparent
642 downward shifts based on comparing recent surveys (2013–2017) to the historical records may be
643 incorrect. Specifically, since the historical records are not necessarily based on systematic surveys of
644 elevational transects, *S. jarrovii* might have actually occurred at the lower elevations documented in
645 2013–2017 during the earlier period (1956–2005), but researchers did not look for them there or
646 found them there but did not collect a specimen to document this. We acknowledge that it is also
647 possible that the upward shifts based on the historical records are underestimated for this same
648 reason. However, in the case of the putative downward shifts, we do have positive evidence that *S.*
649 *jarrovii* can occur at those lower elevations (based on evidence from 2013–2017). Furthermore, it is
650 extremely unclear why *S. jarrovii* would not occur at those lower elevations in the past, since the
651 climate was presumably even more suitable in the historical period (1956–2005) than it was in
652 2013–2017.
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654 Appendix S4. Details on genetic data and analyses

655 Genetic data

656 The genetic dataset was based primarily on individuals sampled (from tail tips) from the time of the
657 initial surveys (2014–2015). Although sample sizes were limited in many mountain ranges, this
658 dataset is invaluable in allowing comparison of populations that are now extinct to those that
659 survived recent climate change. Sampling additional individuals from extinct populations would be
660 difficult.

661 The full RADseq dataset (Wiens et al., 2019) included 119 individuals of *S. jarrovii*. We
662 excluded four individuals from one site because we were not able to revisit this very inaccessible
663 location for resurveys (Apache Peak, Whetstone Mountains). Furthermore, this location was not part
664 of the original transect for this mountain range in 2013–2017, from which other RADseq data for the
665 Whetstones were obtained (Mine Canyon). Moreover, since this location was not a lowest-elevation
666 site it would have been excluded from many analyses.

667 The final primary dataset used (Dataset S5) included 115 individuals, with 1–8 individuals per
668 mountain range (mean=4.37), and 428,203 aligned nucleotide sites. This dataset incorporated 45
669 individuals collected from 1996–2001. We also created a reduced dataset (Dataset S6, $n=70$
670 individuals) containing only genetic samples collected in 2014–2015. Analyses of these two datasets
671 generally gave similar results.

672

673 Populations for genetic analyses

674 We grouped individuals into populations to compare within-population levels of genetic diversity
675 (Datasets S5–S6). Decisions about which individuals were assigned to which populations were made
676 based on their locality (Dataset S4). Specifically, we compared the coordinates via Google Earth
677 (Gorelick et al., 2017) to confirm that individuals were from the same site. In most cases, all
678 individuals from one mountain range were collected along the same elevational transect. If they were
679 from different transects (e.g. different canyons or roads) we split samples from that mountain range
680 into separate populations corresponding to these different localities. Distinguishing these populations
681 also separated the samples collected earlier (1996–2001) from more recent (2014–2015) genetic
682 samples. Different populations within the same mountain range were used for the Chiricahuas,
683 Dragoons, Huachucas, Patagonias, Pinalenos, and Santa Ritas (Table S10). We resurveyed at the
684 specific sites where the genetic material was obtained. Details are given below on the resurveys of
685 these 27 populations, grouped by mountain range. Note that even if we visited the exact coordinates
686 where *S. jarrovii* had been found previously, this did not guarantee that *S. jarrovii* would be found at
687 those exact coordinates. We generally considered a site to be persistent if *S. jarrovii* was found
688 within ~100 meters linear distance of the original site with genetic data and at the same or lower
689 elevation, or if it was further away but was found at lower elevations in the same overall location
690 (e.g. same road or canyon). The persistence of *S. jarrovii* at lower elevations strongly suggested that
691 there was not climate-related local extinction at that location. If genetic samples from one population
692 were obtained from different nearby sites, we used the lowest-elevation site with a genetic sample
693 from that population to calculate the distances to the resurveyed sites. Linear distances between sites
694 were estimated using Google Earth. We considered *S. jarrovii* to be extinct at a local site if it was not
695 found at that site after repeated visits and if it was not found present at lower-elevation sites along
696 that transect (see Appendix S1). Note that all data on the resurveys of sites from which genetic
697 samples were obtained are included in Dataset S1. The time spent searching at each site is also given
698 in Tables S2 and S3 for lowest-elevation sites that went extinct, in Table S4 for low-elevation sites
699 that persisted, and in Table S5 for sites from which genetic data were obtained (that were not the
700 lowest-elevation site on a transect).

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702 **Baboquivaris.** Genetic material (tail tips) was collected here in 2015 at elevations from 1836 m
703 to 1874 m. We resurveyed this site multiple times without finding *S. jarrovii* in 2022 (details in
704 Appendix S1). In 2022, the lowest-elevation *S. jarrovii* on this transect were present at 1981 m. We
705 therefore classified *S. jarrovii* as locally extinct at the site where the genetic data had been collected.

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Canelo Hills. In 2015, genetic material was collected from individuals at an elevation of 1666 m. One *S. jarrovii* individual was found in the resurvey in 2021 at an elevation of 1667 m, 81 meters from the location of the genetic sample, and another *S. jarrovii* was observed at 1672 m, 82 meters from the genetic site (details in Appendix S1). We classified the population at this site as persistent.

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Chiricahuas. In this large and relatively accessible mountain range, genetic samples were collected from several places. We thus grouped the data from this mountain range into 5 subpopulations (Chiricahua 1–5). Samples of Chiricahua 1 (Turkey Creek, Morse Canyon) were collected in 2014 at a putative elevation of 2072 m. We revisited this site twice in 2022. The first time, on 30 May 2022, we found 5 individuals of *S. jarrovii* at elevations from 2032 m to 2149 m. We repeated the survey on 25 June 2022, because the first survey ended 160 meters (linear distance) from the genetic site. On this second visit, we revisited the exact coordinates and found 15 individuals of *S. jarrovii*. The elevations of these individuals ranged from 2067 m up to 2219 m, with the individual at the highest elevation being the closest (~2 meters) to the coordinates of the site where the genetic samples were collected. Note that this is somewhat higher elevation than the value for these coordinates in 2014 (suggesting an error in the original elevation reported), but *S. jarrovii* was clearly extant at many elevations and locations in this canyon (Dataset S1). Individuals were found continuously during this survey (14:05–15:05), and an individual was found immediately upon arriving at the coordinates for the genetic data (15:05), two minutes after finding another individual at a nearby location (15:03).

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Population Chiricahua 2 was a site on Rucker Canyon Road. Genetic material was obtained here in 2015 at an elevation of 1789 m. On a resurvey on 10 April 2022, we found 3 *S. jarrovii* 130 meters from the genetic site, at the same elevation as the genetic sample site and below (between 1783 m and 1789 m). The first individual was found after 8 minutes (14:44–14:52) and a total of three individuals were found in 16 minutes.

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Two other populations were in Cave Creek Canyon. Genetic material was collected at both sites in 2015. One population (Chiricahua-3) was on the east side of the canyon close to the town of Portal, at an elevation of 1497 m. We revisited the site on 5 June 2022 and observed 5 *S. jarrovii* including 2 newborn individuals at elevations between 1490 m to 1501 m (closest distance to genetic site: 18 meters). These were found over ~34 minutes (see Appendix S1), and the first was found immediately upon arriving at this location. The other population (Chiricahua-4) was close to the Idlewild and Stewart Campgrounds at an elevation of 1534 m. We revisited this site on 3 September 2022 and found two individuals that were 110 and 1.5 meters away from the lowest-elevation site with a genetic sample for this population, at elevations of 1531 and 1533 m. We found two individuals in ~24 minutes (12:50–13:14), the first after only 5 minutes (12:55).

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A fifth population (Chiricahua-5) occurs along road Farm Road 42 near East Turkey Creek, at an elevation of 1957 m. These genetic samples were collected in 1996, 2000, and 2001. We visited this site on 5 June 2022 and found 3 *S. jarrovii* (including one newborn) at the same site (closest distance to the genetic site: 20 meters). All were found within 5 minutes (10:17–10:22), and the first was found immediately upon arriving at this location.

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All five subpopulations of the Chiricahuas were considered to be persistent populations given that individuals were found in relatively close proximity to the genetic sites in 2022, and at equivalent or lower elevations.

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Coyotes. Genetic samples in the Coyotes were collected in 2015 at 1589 m and 1593 m elevation. We resurveyed the same rock outcrops where the genetic samples were collected on 29 March 2022 and again on 23 April 2022 (Appendix S1). We did not find individuals of *S. jarrovii* at these sites. Therefore, this population was classified as locally extinct. Furthermore, *S. clarkii* was found in the rock outcrops where *S. jarrovii* was seen in 2015, on both visits, supporting the absence of *S. jarrovii* there. *Sceloporus jarrovii* was found 116 meters linear distance from the genetic sampling site, but at a higher elevation of 1605 m (see Appendix S1).

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Dos Cabezas. Genetic samples were collected in the Dos Cabezas in 2015 along an elevational transect from 1305 m to 1368 m. The site was revisited two times. First, on 3 April 2021, two *S. jarrovi* were found 170 meters from the lowest-elevation molecular site at elevations of 1259 m and 1279 m (but we did not survey within 100 meters of the genetic site on that date). Second, on 3 July 2022, three individuals were observed within 90 meters of the molecular site (the highest at 1270 m). All were found within 33 minutes (10:22–11:05), and the first was found immediately. The one closest to the molecular site was found after looking for 10 minutes (10:55–11:05). We categorized the population here as persistent, especially given that individuals were present at lower elevations than the molecular sites, and because all sites were in the same canyon.

Dragoons. Genetic samples from the Dragoons were split into two populations. One population (Dragoons 1) was collected in 2015 at an elevation of 1579 m and 1651 m at Cochise Stronghold. We resurveyed that area twice. On 10 April 2021, an individual of *S. jarrovi* was found immediately at the entrance to the campground, which is 1.6 km from the nearest genetic site and lower in elevation (1490 m). On the same survey, another individual was found at 1503 m and 1.2 km from the lower genetic sample site. However, we did not focus specifically on revisiting the site from which the genetic samples were obtained on that survey. In the second survey on 16 April 2022, we went to the exact site from which the genetic sample was obtained and found *S. jarrovi* present 40 meters from that site, at an elevation of 1578 m. This individual was found after looking for ~23 minutes (17:10–17:33). A total of four individuals were found on the Cochise Stronghold Trail over the course 1:03 hours (16:30–17:33). We classified the population at this genetic site as persistent, especially given their presence at lower elevations.

A second population (Dragoons 2) was along China Peak Road at 1981 m, with genetic samples collected in 1998. We surveyed this site on 16 April 2022 and recorded *S. jarrovi* at 12 meters linear distance from the original site at an elevation of 1977 m. This individual was found immediately upon arrival at the site (15:25), before we could exit the vehicle. This population was also classified as persistent.

Galiuros. In the Galiuros, genetic material was collected in 2014 at 1654 m elevation near Deer Creek Ranch. The site was resurveyed on 20 February 2021. We found *S. jarrovi* at the same rock outcrop, within 10 meters of the site from which genetic samples were obtained, at an elevation of 1648 m (see Appendix S1). Thus, the population at this site was classified as persistent.

Huachucas. Genetic samples from the Huachucas were grouped into two populations. One population (Huachucas 1) was sampled in 2014 between 1887 m and 1907 m elevation in Scotia Canyon (south side of the Huachucas). We revisited this canyon (but not the exact site) on 8 May 2021 and found *S. jarrovi* at an elevation of 1776 m (2.8 km linear distance) to confirm the persistence at the lowest-elevation site. The exact site for the genetic samples was resurveyed on 10 July 2022 and a total of 9 *S. jarrovi* were found at elevations from 1845 m up to 1912 m, over the course of 2:02 hours (11:00–13:02). The closest individual was recorded within 110 meters linear distance (elevation 1912 m) of the original site from which genetic samples were obtained. The first individual was found after 3 minutes (11:03), whereas the individual closest to the site was found immediately upon arriving there (12:06). We classified the population as persistent, especially given their presence at lower elevations.

A second population (Huachucas 2) was sampled in 1998 and 2001 at an elevation of 2029 m in Carr Canyon (north side of the Huachucas). We resurveyed this site twice. First, on 30 May 2022, we found *S. jarrovi* below (1993 m elevation, 370 meters linear distance) and above (2039 m elevation, 200 meters distance) the site from which genetic samples were obtained, but not at the site itself. We searched at this site for 29 minutes (10:27–10:56). Since the site with genetic samples is relatively unshaded and we arrived relatively late in the morning, the lizards might have been hidden in crevices. We searched a second time on 18 June 2022 and arrived earlier when temperatures were

810 lower (9:00). This time, we found *S. jarrovii* close to the genetic sample site (2021 m elevation, 30
 811 meters linear distance), after searching for 6 minutes (9:00–9:06). We classified this population as
 812 persistent.

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814 **Little Dragons.** Genetic material was collected in Texas Canyon in 2014 and 2015 both times
 815 at an elevation of 1450 m. We revisited this site on 27 February 2021 but did not find *S. jarrovii*
 816 present. We searched for approximately 47 minutes (15:20–16:07). On 10 April 2021, we found 2
 817 individuals at 100 meters linear distance from the closest site where the genetic samples were
 818 obtained, and at similar elevations (1452 m and 1446 m). These were found after 23 minutes of
 819 searching (10:05–10:28), the first after 19 minutes (10:24). Thus, we considered the population at
 820 this site as persistent.

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822 **Mules.** Genetic samples were collected in 2014 at elevations between 1748 and 1805 m at a site
 823 near Guest Road, west of Mule Pass. This location was resurveyed three times (8 May 2021, 7
 824 August 2021, 25 June 2022; see Appendix S1). No *S. jarrovii* were found, but *S. clarkii* was found at
 825 the lowest elevation site (Appendix S1). This population was therefore classified as extinct.
 826 Repeated surveys at higher elevations in this mountain range also revealed apparent local extinction
 827 of *S. jarrovii*, except close to the peak of Mount Ballard (see Appendix S1).

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829 **Patagonias.** In the Patagonias, one genetic sample was collected in 2015 at an elevation of 1773
 830 m on the west side of the main ridge. This was classified as population Patagonias-1. We revisited
 831 this site on 20 March 2021 and found 2 *S. jarrovii*. The closest was 54 meters linear distance from
 832 the genetic sample site, at an elevation of 1780 m. We searched above 1700 m for 8 minutes before
 833 finding the first individual. On 20 June 2021 we visited the site a second time, observing 3
 834 individuals at elevations from 1626 m to 1795 m with the closest observation 209 meters from the
 835 genetic site. We considered the population at this site as persistent, especially given the presence of
 836 *S. jarrovii* at lower elevations.

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838 Genetic material was collected in 1998 at a different site at an elevation of 1778 m. This site
 839 (Patagonias 2) is also along Duquesne Road but approximately 1 km further east (east side of the
 840 main ridge). We visited this site on 18 June 2022 and found *S. jarrovii* 160 meters from the genetic
 841 site at an elevation of 1782 m. We found 3 individuals in 29 minutes of searching this area (11:40–
 842 12:09), the first after 4 minutes (11:44). In the same survey, we also found *S. jarrovii* along the same
 843 transect at elevations of 1802 m (690 m linear distance) and 1728 m (1.5 km linear distance). We
 844 classified the population at this site as persistent, especially given their presence at both lower and
 845 higher elevations.

846

847 **Perillas.** In 2014, one genetic sample was obtained at 1833 m elevation on the northern slope of
 848 North College Peak. We resurveyed this site on 10 April 2022, and recorded *S. jarrovii* slightly
 849 below (1830 m) and 71 meters distant from the genetic sample site. We found another individual at
 850 an elevation of 1849 m and only 28 meters from the genetic sample site. As noted in Appendix S1, at
 851 higher elevations (>1795 m) a total of three individuals of *S. jarrovii* were found in ~28 minutes
 852 (10:27–10:55; 1797–1849 m), with the first individuals found after ~12 minutes (10:27–10:39;
 1797–1830 m). We classified this population as persistent.

853

854 **Pinalenos.** In 1998 genetic samples were collected at two different locations in the Pinalenos.
 855 One site (Pinalenos-1) was along State Route 366 at 2141 m. We resurveyed this site on 5 June 2022
 856 and *S. jarrovii* was found 260 meters from the original site at an elevation of 2166 m. This individual
 857 was found more-or-less immediately (15:57). Individuals were also found along the same road at
 858 lower elevations on previous surveys in 2021–2022 (Appendix S1). The second site (Pinalenos-2)
 859 was on Tripp Canyon Road at an elevation of 1895 m. We surveyed this site on 5 June 2022 and
 860 found an individual of *S. jarrovii* at an elevation of 1881 m, 33 meters from the genetic site, 7

861 minutes after we began searching this area (13:51–13:58). The populations were considered to be
 862 persistent at both of these sites.

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864 **Quinlans.** In the Quinlans, genetic samples were collected in 1998 at an elevation of 1921 m,
 865 along the road to Kitt Peak. We could not visit this exact site in 2021 or 2022, because the area close
 866 to Kitt Peak was closed to the public due to the covid pandemic. However, we surveyed at lower
 867 elevations along the road to Kitt Peak on 25 March 2022 and found 2 individuals of *S. jarrovii*
 868 within 860 meters of the genetic site, at elevations of 1775 m and 1771 m (Dataset S1). The two
 869 individuals were found in only 6 minutes (8:25–8:31), and the first was found immediately as soon
 870 as we began searching suitable habitat. Given the presence of this species nearby at lower elevations,
 871 we assumed that the higher-elevation population in the Quinlans is persistent.

872

873 **Santa Ritas.** There were two populations sampled for genetic data in this mountain range. One
 874 population (Santa Ritas 1) was in Madera Canyon on a hillside above Madera Creek and adjacent to
 875 the Super Trail, sampled in 2014 at 1670 m elevation. We surveyed this area three times (31 May
 876 2021, 11 October 2021, 3 April 2022). We found the closest *S. jarrovii* at 82 m distance from the
 877 genetic site in the first resurvey at an elevation of 1663 m. In the second resurvey, we found an
 878 individual lower (1628 m), 126 meters from the genetic site. In the third survey here, we found *S.*
 879 *jarrovii* within 156 meters at 1695 m elevation. Below an elevation of 1628 m *S. jarrovii* was found
 880 to be absent in Madera Creek. At the exact molecular site, we did not find *S. jarrovii* even after six
 881 surveys: on 15 May 2021 (18:45), 31 May 2021 (9:50–9:56), 11 October 2021 (10:59), 3 April 2021
 882 (16:00), 30 April 2021 (13:30–13:38), and 2 June 2022 (9:58–10:06 and 10:39). This site is located
 883 in rock outcrops on top of a hill, and *S. jarrovii* found in the resurveys were in rock outcrops close to
 884 the creek bed (hence, linear distance does not indicate that these are distinct sites). This site was
 885 classified as locally extinct in the main analysis. However, we also included an alternative analysis
 886 in which this site was instead considered to be persistent.

887 The second population (Santa Ritas 2) was sampled for genetic data in 1997 and was located on
 888 Mount Hopkins Road at an elevation of 2148 m. We visited this site on 30 April 2022 and found *S.*
 889 *jarrovii* present at an elevation of 2151 m, 48 meters from the exact coordinates of the genetic
 890 samples. We thus considered this population as persistent. The individual was found immediately
 891 upon arriving at the site (16:02).

892

893 **Santa Teresas.** Genetic samples were collected in Buford Canyon at elevations from 1586 m to
 894 1592 m in 2015. We revisited the site twice. On 3 April 2021 we found no *S. jarrovii*. We also
 895 revisited the site on 15 August 2021, and found *S. jarrovii* present at 1585 m, 77 meters from the
 896 closest site with genetic data. We classified the population at this site as persistent.

897

898 **Whetstones.** Genetic samples were collected in 2015 at an elevation of 2087 m on the western
 899 ridge above Mine Canyon. We resurveyed this site on 19 March 2022 and found *S. jarrovii* on the
 900 same rock outcrop where genetic samples were collected (within 13 meters of the genetic site) at an
 901 elevation of 2092 m. Genetic samples were also collected at Apache Peak in 2015. This site was not
 902 revisited due to its inaccessibility and it was excluded from further analyses.

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904 **Winchesters.** Genetic samples were collected west of Warbonnet Ranch in 2015 at elevations
 905 from 1867 m to 1920 m. We resurveyed this transect three times (16 October 2021, 15 March 2022,
 906 16 April 2022). We found *S. jarrovii* only on 16 April 2022 (details in Appendix S1). This individual
 907 was recorded at 1919 m, 130 meters from the lowest-elevation site with genetic data. Since we were
 908 not able to find any *S. jarrovii* at the lowest elevation from 2015, we considered the population at
 909 this lowest edge to be locally extinct. However, in an alternative analysis we considered this site as
 910 persistent given that genetic samples were collected along an elevational gradient up to the elevation
 911 where we recorded *S. jarrovii* in 2022.

912

913 Genetic diversity analyses

914 We estimated genetic diversity within populations using a measure of nucleotide diversity (π). This
 915 index is based on the average number of nucleotide differences per site between two DNA
 916 sequences, using all possible pairs of individuals in the sampled population (Nei & Li, 1979). The
 917 populations used were those described above (Dataset S4). We first converted the RADseq dataset
 918 from the given phylip format (available from <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.dp13668>) into fasta
 919 format (Dataset S5: including genetic samples collected in 1996–2001 and in 2014–2015; Dataset
 920 S6: only samples from 2014–2015). We used the alignment viewer and editor AliView (Larson,
 921 2014). Sequences of outgroup taxa (not *S. jarrovii*) were deleted.

922 For calculation of nucleotide diversity (π) we used the command-line based software *pixy*
 923 (Korunes & Samuk, 2021). However, this required some processing beforehand. First, we
 924 reconstructed heterozygous sites to account for sites with IUPAC ambiguity codes using the
 925 “unfold” option in the software DnaSP v.6 (Rozas et al., 2017). Next, we converted the unfolded
 926 fasta file into an all-sites vcf file using the command-line tool SNPsites (Page et al., 2016). To keep
 927 all sites of the alignment (not only the polymorphic sites) we used the optional command “-b”. Next,
 928 we used this all-sites vcf file in *pixy* to estimate nucleotide diversity with the command “-stats pi”
 929 and a size of 428,203 sites, covering the full aligned sequence length. The number of variants was
 930 checked with the command `grep -vc '#'`.

931 Populations represented by a single individual were excluded from population-wide genetic
 932 diversity analyses since the estimation within a single individual might not be equivalent to the
 933 comparison between two or more individuals. This was the case for the Perillas in both datasets and
 934 the Patagonias in Dataset S6 (only one individual from recent genetic collections). Estimates of
 935 genetic variation within each population are in Dataset S7.

936 Genetic diversity analyses were performed with the primary dataset (with all individuals; Dataset
 937 S5) and the secondary dataset (only individuals from 2014–2015; Dataset S6). We tested if π differed
 938 between samples collected in 1996–2001 and those collected in 2014–2015 with t-tests. An unpaired
 939 t-test comparing all recent vs. all earlier collected samples was not significant ($p=0.186$; $n=25$
 940 populations). The difference was also not significant when pairing samples from the same mountain
 941 range ($p=0.201$; $n=11$ populations from 4 mountain ranges with genetic data from both time
 942 periods). Therefore, the main analyses combined these sets of samples. However, we also performed
 943 alternative analyses that used only the more recent samples (2014–2015). These analyses generally
 944 gave similar results (Tables S14–S15). We also performed analyses that included only the lowest-
 945 edge populations from each mountain range. These latter analyses also show that the results are not
 946 explained by including more than one population per mountain range.

947 We found that populations that went extinct generally had lower genetic diversity than those that
 948 remained persistent (see Results). However, it is hypothetically possible that these populations went
 949 extinct because their genetic diversity was already low, rather than because of recent climate change.
 950 To test for changes in population size before the genetic samples were collected, we also estimated
 951 Tajima’s D within each population (Tajima, 1989). We used *DnaSP* v.6 and applied the analysis
 952 “Tajimas Test”. Positive values of Tajima’s D indicate recent population contraction and negative
 953 values indicate a recent expansion (Schmidt & Pool, 2002). Therefore, if populations that went
 954 extinct recently were already in decline before the initial survey in 2013–2017, we might expect to
 955 see a difference in Tajima’s D between currently persistent and extinct populations, with extinct
 956 populations having more positive values. However, we found that values were generally positive for
 957 both extinct and persistent populations (Dataset S7), and that there was no significant difference in
 958 values of Tajima’s D between these sets of populations (mean D for $n=5$ extinct populations=0.269,
 959 mean D for $n=20$ persistent populations=0.179; $p=0.655$, unpaired t-test; $n=25$ populations as shown
 960 in Table S10; Datasets S5, S7). Note that the Patagonias and Perillas were excluded here because
 961 they were each represented by a single sampled individual.

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965 **Candidate SNPs**

966 We primarily used the RADseq data to assess the relationship between genetic diversity and
 967 population survival (or extinction) in the face of climate change. We also used these data to search
 968 for candidate allelic variants that might have helped certain low-elevation populations survive recent
 969 climate change. However, there are important caveats that are associated with these latter analyses.
 970 First, we used RADseq data. Many other authors have used this approach to scan genomes and
 971 identify climate-related loci (e.g. Bay et al., 2018; Capblancq et al., 2020), but RADseq datasets
 972 include sequences for only small portions of the total genome, which makes their usage to find
 973 potentially adaptive loci somewhat controversial (e.g. Catchen et al., 2017; Lowry et al., 2017a,b;
 974 McKinney et al., 2017). Although we do find potentially relevant loci, it should be understood that
 975 there may be many unsampled loci that are also relevant. Even among the SNPs included here, we
 976 only considered those SNPs that were the most strongly associated with climatic variables, to be
 977 conservative. Therefore, there might be additional relevant loci, even among those sampled here.
 978 Third, we do not generally know the function of these loci, and how they might be related to
 979 surviving climate change (if they are). Therefore, these results should be considered very
 980 preliminary.

981 We first used a latent factor mixed model (LFMM) to scan the RADseq data for loci that
 982 were strongly correlated with climatic variables. This is an individual-based approach, for which we
 983 aligned each individual's genetic data (Dataset S5) with the climatic data from the location where
 984 that individual was sampled (Dataset S8). We uploaded the aligned sequences in fasta format into R
 985 using *adegenet*. The data was converted to a *genind* object, comprising 115 individuals, 1609 RAD
 986 loci, and 3218 alleles (SNPs). Note that each locus could have >1 SNPs. We then extracted the allele
 987 frequency matrix and scanned it for missing data. The matrix had 15.05% missing data, which could
 988 cause problems for fitting the LFMM (Wagner, 2022). Therefore, we replaced the sites with missing
 989 data with the most common genotype at each SNP across all individuals (Wagner, 2022). However,
 990 when analyzing the presence of identified candidate SNPs within populations, we used the
 991 unmodified data including these missing data (as shown in Table S20).

992 We included the same five climatic variables used in our other climatic analyses (Dataset S8).
 993 Each variable was tested in an individual LFMM model, executed with the R package *lfmm* (Caye et
 994 al., 2019). Since LFMMs account for background population structure, the estimated number of
 995 latent factors in the data (K) must be determined. Following recommendations (François et al.,
 996 2016), we used the number of genetic clusters within the dataset, which was estimated in a previous
 997 study (Wiens et al., 2019). Among the 18 mountain ranges sampled, the individuals from 17 each
 998 cluster into monophyletic groups (all but the Huachucas). Therefore, we set K=17. We also tested the
 999 model fit with alternative K-values of 16 and 18 (Wagner, 2022), but K=17 resulted in genomic
 000 inflation factors (GIFs) the closest to 1, representing a good model fit (François et al., 2016; Wagner,
 001 2022). The final LFMMs were performed with the function “*lfmm_ridge*” in the *lfmm* package.

002 For processing the model output, we first checked the GIF and plotted the *p*-values (François et
 003 al., 2016; Frichot et al., 2013; Wagner, 2022). Second, we adjusted the *p*-values using the GIF to
 004 generate a uniform histogram with a peak near zero (indicating a correct null hypothesis, with most
 005 SNPs neutral except for the candidate SNPs). The unadjusted and adjusted final histograms are
 006 shown in Fig. S7. Third, we applied a False Discovery Rate (FDR) control method by converting *p*-
 007 values to *q*-values using the *qvalue* package from Bioconductor (Storey & Bass, 2003). The *q*-values
 008 are a measure of individual SNP significance while accounting for multiple testing (Storey & Bass,
 009 2003). In the last step, we identified candidate SNPs below the chosen, conservative FDR threshold
 010 (FDR<0.01). The FDR threshold is marked in the Manhattan plots in Fig. S5. Every SNP above this
 011 line was considered significant.

012 We note that there are many possible methods that can be used to identify genotype-environment
 013 associations from genomic data (e.g. Forester et al., 2018; Capblancq et al., 2020). We chose LFMM
 014 because it can potentially accommodate strong population structure (Frichot et al., 2013), and has
 015 been widely used in studies of this type (Capblancq et al., 2020). *Sceloporus jarrovi* in southeastern
 016 Arizona clearly has strong population structure, given that it is distributed among 18 montane Sky

017 Islands, most of which have been separated from each other for a million years or more (Wiens et al.,
 018 2019). Although the RDA approach (redundancy analysis) performs well in simulations with weak
 019 population structure, simulations suggest that it may not be advantageous when there is strong
 020 population structure (Forester et al., 2018). Furthermore, it has been argued that combining LFMM
 021 and RDA may not be beneficial and may introduce biases instead (Forester et al., 2018). Finally, we
 022 emphasize that our analyses focus on the SNPs that are most strongly associated with climatic
 023 variables. We could potentially find many additional SNPs and candidate alleles using alternative
 024 methods for obtaining genomic data and testing for genotype-environment associations.

025

026 **Candidate genes**

027 For all five climate variables, we found a limited number of SNPs (two to three) which showed a
 028 much stronger correlation with the climatic variables than the other candidate SNPs (Fig. S5).
 029 Therefore, we investigated the top three SNPs (with the highest q -value) for each climatic variable in
 030 more detail. For each of these SNPs, we chose the region containing the candidate SNP with a frame
 031 of ~20 bp (base pairs). The sequences and position of the SNPs are given in Table S19. We located
 032 the region in the software AliView (<https://ormbunkar.se/aliview/>; Larson, 2014). We next copied
 033 the sequence of interest into the Web BLAST application of the NCBI database
 034 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). Since our dataset consisted of aligned RADseq fragments, we
 035 initially tested which sequence lengths would give the best fit to the reference genome of *Sceloporus*
 036 *undulatus* (the most closely related species with a sequenced genome). Hence, we applied the NCBI
 037 BLAST function on sequences of various lengths to investigate the match to the reference genome. If
 038 we chose sequences longer than 20 bp, no proper alignment was generated. Instead, the query
 039 sequences were split into smaller pieces by the BLAST algorithm and only the individual fragments
 040 were matched to the reference genome, with gaps in between the fragments. However, with
 041 sequences shorter than 20 bp, the uniqueness of the sequences decreased and thus the E-values
 042 (Expect-value, the number of hits expected by chance) generally increased. Therefore, we chose a
 043 length of approximately 20 bp as the most appropriate to obtain the highest coverage and lowest E-
 044 value possible (i.e. the most accurate result). We slightly varied the length and the position of the
 045 candidate SNP within this region to achieve the best fit to the reference genome. We used only hits
 046 which included the SNP locus, since we were interested in the effect of changes at this particular
 047 site.

048 We then examined the position of top candidate SNPs within the *Sceloporus undulatus* reference
 049 genome using the graphic interface of the NCBI BLAST application. This shows the match of the
 050 query sequence to the reference, including potential genes and several other features. We evaluated
 051 whether the SNP was located within an annotated gene (i.e. if there were descriptions and amino-
 052 acid sequences of the gene available). If the SNP was in a known gene, we evaluated the location
 053 within the gene and if a change in this nucleotide position was a synonymous or non-synonymous
 054 change. Only a non-synonymous change would change the amino acid sequence and thus have the
 055 potential to be important functionally. We note that most candidate genes were generally annotated
 056 (i.e. known overall length, name of the gene, function). However, the amino-acid sequences of the
 057 specific parts of the gene in which the candidate SNPs occurred were not known for most genes.

058 Next, we used the UniProt database (<https://www.uniprot.org/>) to investigate the potential
 059 functions of the genes that contained these SNPs. We searched for the genes of interest within the
 060 genomes of two lizard species with sequenced genomes. We preferentially used the green anole
 061 (*Anolis carolinensis*) which is a pleurodont iguanian lizard, like *S. jarrovi*. We used the more
 062 distantly related wall lizard (*Podarcis muralis*) if there was no available information on the gene of
 063 interest for *A. carolinensis*. Note that the species *Sceloporus undulatus* (the reference genome used
 064 for finding candidate SNPs) was not available in the UniProt database. These two species (*A.*
 065 *carolinensis*, *P. muralis*) are the phylogenetically closest and most thoroughly annotated genomes
 066 available in this database. One gene (FNDC3A) was not annotated for these species, and we
 067 therefore referred to the function within the mouse genome (Table S18).

068 We hypothesized that extinct populations might lack mutations in climate-associated SNPs that
069 would allow them to persist in warmer climates. We compared the identity of the specific nucleotide
070 bases for the top candidate SNPs within persistent and extinct populations. For this, we located the
071 position of the candidate SNP within the alignment and extracted the base at this position for each
072 individual sample. Then, we counted the percentage of individuals with each base within each
073 population (Table S20). Individuals heterozygous at candidate SNP sites were counted as 50% of an
074 individual for each of the two bases present. Some individuals had missing data at the position of the
075 candidate SNP, because the entire locus was absent in that individual. We removed individuals with
076 missing data from the calculation of nucleotide frequencies. Given that the entire locus was missing
077 in each case, the missing data presumably do not reflect functionally meaningful variation in the
078 length of the gene, such as a missing codon triplet.
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083 **FIGURE S1. Upward elevational shifts in the lower-elevation range limits of *Sceloporus***

084 ***jarrovi* populations over time, focusing on historical records versus more recent surveys.** A

085 total of 12 transects (10 mountain ranges) had comparable data (same transects) between the historic

086 records (1956–2005) and the initial surveys (2013–2017). Cadet blue circles represent the initial

087 lowest elevation limit on each transect (historic), whereas orange triangles show the new lowest

088 elevational limits estimated in 2013–2017. Transects with only cadet blue circles indicate those

089 transects with no upward changes in elevational distribution between surveys. Mountain ranges

090 lacking relevant historical records are not shown. MASL=meters above sea level. Data are in Table

091 S7.

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 094 **FIGURE S2. Comparing upper elevational range limits of *Sceloporus clarkii* and *S. jarrovi***
 095 **over time on 17 mountain ranges in southeastern Arizona.** (a) A juvenile of *S. clarkii*. This
 096 species generally occurs at lower elevations than *S. jarrovi* and its upper elevational limits in the
 097 region seem to be constrained by the presence of *S. jarrovi*, with *S. clarkii* occurring at higher
 098 elevations in mountain ranges where *S. jarrovi* is absent (Wiens et al., 2019). (b) Upper elevational
 099 range limits of *Sceloporus clarkii* and lower elevational range limits of *S. jarrovi* in the initial
 100 surveys and resurveys. Elevational range limits (in meters above sea level) are shown for 20
 101 transects (17 mountain ranges) in the initial survey (2013–2017; circles) and resurveys (2021–2022;
 102 triangles). These results also include transects where we recorded *S. clarkii* only in one of the survey
 103 periods (initial only: Canelo Hills, Dragoons, Galiuros, Huachuucas, Patagonias; resurvey only:
 104 Perillas). Transects lacking *S. clarkii* entirely are excluded (only Dos Cabezas). Transects with only
 105 circles indicate those with no upward changes in elevational distribution between surveys. Data are
 106 shown in Table S6. Note that *S. jarrovi* generally occurs above *S. clarkii* and that *S. clarkii* shifted
 107 upward where there were large upward shifts in the lower elevational limit of *S. jarrovi*.

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FIGURE S3. Correlations between upward elevational shifts in *Sceloporus jarrovii* and *S. clarkii*. (a) Correlations between total upward elevational changes ($r=0.717$, $p=0.045$, $n=8$) in both species. (b) Rates of upward elevational changes in both species ($r=0.532$, $p=0.175$, $n=8$). The only transects included are those on which both *S. jarrovii* and *S. clarkii* shifted upwards, since we predicted that upward shifts in *S. jarrovii* allow upward shifts in *S. clarkii*. Shifts are between the original surveys in 2013–2017 and the resurveys in 2021–2022. Gray shows 95% confidence interval. Data are in Table S6.

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FIGURE S4. Correlations between genetic variation and niche change among populations.

Correlations of nucleotide diversity (π) in persistent lowest-edge *Sceloporus jarrovi* populations (cadet blue dots, $n=6$) and niche change for the five climatic variables: mean annual temperature (MAT: $r=0.648$, $p=0.116$), mean warmest month temperature (MWMT: $r=0.795$, $p=0.033$), mean annual precipitation (MAP: $r=-0.131$, $p=0.780$), degree-days below 0°C (DD0: $r=0.028$, $p=0.952$), and Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit (CMD: $r=-0.112$, $p=0.811$). Statistical tests are Pearson's product moment correlations. Gray shows 95% confidence interval. Data are in Datasets S7–S8.

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FIGURE S5. Manhattan plots of latent-factor mixed-model (LFMM) results. A total of 3,218 SNPs from the full dataset ($n=115$ individuals; Dataset S5) were tested for their correlation with the five climate variables: MAT=mean annual temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); MWMT=mean warmest month temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); MAP=mean annual precipitation (mm); DD0=degree-days below 0°C (days); and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit (mm). Dotted lines show the FDR threshold (1%). Each blue point shows the adjusted p -value (q -value) of the correlation between the climate variable and the frequency of the specific SNP. All points above the dotted line are considered significant.

137 **FIGURE S6. Elevational and climatic variation among extinct and persistent lowest-edge**
 138 **populations with climate-related genetic variants.** Only the 13 mountain ranges in which the
 139 lowest-elevation populations were sampled for genetic data (in 2014–2015) are included. We
 140 identified eight candidate SNPs that were strongly related to variation in climate across all
 141 populations (Table S17). Among these 13 populations, these variants occurred at four loci in the Dos
 142 Cabezas (SNPs 224233, 404828, 156479, 224005; fixed or almost fixed), at one locus in the Little
 143 Dragons (SNP 62550; fixed), and at two loci in the Perillas (SNPs 404828, 156479; fixed). These
 144 three populations are therefore shown as having one or more of these genetic variants, although they
 145 occur at low frequencies in some other populations (Table S20). Populations exposed to higher
 146 temperatures were expected to go extinct, but these climate-associated genetic variants were present
 147 in populations that persisted at the three warmest sites (highest mean annual temperature, MAT).
 148 These variants were absent in the five extinct populations. Climatic data are in Dataset S8.
 149 MWM=mean warmest month temperature; MAP=mean annual precipitation; DD0=degree-days
 150 below 0°C; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit.

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FIGURE S7. Histograms of p -value adjustments for latent-factor mixed models. Distributions of unadjusted p -values (left) and adjusted p -values ($=q$ -value, right) between 0 and 1 (with frequency in total values) for $n=3218$ SNPs (Dataset S5, $n=115$ individuals). The SNPs were tested for their association with the five climate variables: MAT=mean annual temperature, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in $^{\circ}\text{C}$; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DDO=degree-days below 0°C , in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm.

161 **TABLE S1. Meta-analysis of shifts in lowest-elevation range edges.** We used a modified version
 162 of the dataset from a published meta-analysis (Rumpf et al., 2019) to estimate rates of range shifts.
 163 That dataset summarized information on range shifts from 22 published studies. The start year is the
 164 year of the initial survey, and the end year is the midpoint year of the resurvey. Resurvey dates are
 165 the set of years over which the resurvey of the elevational transect occurred. Midpoint values were
 166 used when a survey period spanned multiple years. Duration was calculated from the year of the
 167 initial survey (Start year) to the midpoint year of the resurvey (End year). Negative values of shifts
 168 and shift rates indicate that species lowest-elevation range limit moved downward in elevation over
 169 time, whereas positive values indicate an upward shift. Each estimated rate is the average among the
 170 species in each study (rates for each species in Dataset S2).
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Taxon	Start year (mean)	End year (mean)	Resurvey dates	Duration (years)	Shift (m)	Shift rate (m/year)	Source
plant	1966.5	2008	2008	41.5	-107.00	-2.58	Angelo & Daehler (2013)
plant	1963	2011	2011	48.0	125.00	2.60	Brusca et al. (2013)
plant	1953	2003	2003	50.0	-48.00	-0.96	Cannone & Pignatti (2014)
invertebrate	1965	2007	2007	42.0	234.46	5.58	Chen et al. (2011)
vertebrate	1986	2006	2003– 2009	20.0	4.78	0.24	Comte & Grenouillet (2013)
plant	1900	2008	2008	108.0	77.55	0.72	Felde et al. (2012)
vertebrate	1965	2012.5	2012– 2013	47.5	93.69	1.97	Freeman & Class Freeman (2014)
plant	1909	2006	2006	97.0	113.81	1.17	Frei et al. (2010)
vertebrate	1962	2009	2007– 2011	47.0	208.01	4.43	Harris et al. (2012)
plant	1961	2010	2010	49.0	-101.67	-2.07	Kopp & Cleland (2014)
invertebrate	1970	2011	2011	41.0	84.00	1.71	Lindholm et al. (2012)
invertebrate	1987	2006.5	2006– 2007	19.5	47.63	2.44	Menéndez et al. (2014)
invertebrate	1970	2005	2004– 2006	35.0	290.00	8.29	Merrill et al. (2008)
vertebrate	1917	2004.5	2003– 2006	87.5	166.09	1.90	Moritz et al. (2008)
vertebrate	1943.5	2011	2011	67.5	-83.14	-1.23	Moskwik (2014)
invertebrate	1988.5	2008	2007– 2009	19.5	174.00	8.92	Ploquin et al. (2013)
vertebrate	1993	2003	2003	10.0	76.17	7.62	Raxworthy et al. (2008)
vertebrate	1928	2007	2006– 2008	79.0	62.50	0.79	Rowe et al. (2010)
plant	1969.5	2014.5	2014– 2015	74.0	29.82	0.40	Rumpf et al. (2018)
plant	1849.5	2008.5	2007– 2010	159.0	256.98	1.62	Telwala et al. (2013)
vertebrate	1915	1993	1980– 2006	78.0	-35.48	-0.45	Tingley et al. (2012)
invertebrate	1970	2004	2004	34.0	134.22	3.95	Wilson et al. (2005)

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174 **TABLE S2. Summary of searches of sites with inferred local extinction.** Only transects with
 175 apparent local extinction of the lowest-elevation sites are included here. The date (month/day/year)
 176 and duration of each survey are given (duration is only for the area of the relevant sites; details in
 177 Appendix S1). This summary also shows whether *S. jarrovii* was found at higher elevations on the
 178 same transect on the day of the survey, if it was found at another location on that same day (yes or no
 179 is only given if there was a search at another location, and a no indicates that it was not found at the
 180 other location on that day), if the transect was the only location surveyed that day, and if other lizard
 181 species were found on that same transect that day. Note that for some transects, some surveys did not
 182 extend to high enough elevations to find *S. jarrovii* at elevations where it was found in other (later)
 183 resurveys. These cases are indicated with an asterisk. Finding *S. jarrovii* at new sites at higher
 184 elevations often required more visits and time than finding them again at previously recorded sites.
 185 On the first resurveys of the Baboquivaris and Winchesters we found a large individual of
 186 *Sceloporus* at high elevations that could not be identified to species before it fled into a crevice
 187 (either *S. clarkii* or *S. jarrovii*). Subsequent visits confirmed the presence of *S. jarrovii* at these sites.
 188 For other species, we list whether another lizard species was found on the transect that day. For
 189 “Other species”, we list the closest relative of *S. jarrovii* found, either *S. clarkii* or (if *S. clarkii* was
 190 not found) then *Urosaurus ornatus*.
 191

Transect	Date	Duration	Same transect?	Other location?	Only transect?	Other species?
Baboquivaris	4/2/22	0:40	no?		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Baboquivaris	4/29/22	1:00	yes		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Coyotes*	3/25/22	0:40	no	yes (Quinlans)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Coyotes	4/23/22	0:40	yes	no (Quinlans)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Mules, Guest Road	5/8/21	0:53	no	yes (Canelo Hills, Chiricahuas)	no	no
Mules, Guest Road	8/7/21	0:54	no		yes	no
Mules, Guest Road	6/25/22	0:49	no	yes (Chiricahuas)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Mules, Juniper Flats	10/2/21	0:33	no		yes	<i>U. ornatus</i>
Mules, Juniper Flats	3/19/22	0:20	no	yes (Whetstones)	no	no
Mules, Juniper Flats	6/25/22	0:34	no	yes (Chiricahuas)	no	<i>U. ornatus</i>
Mules, Mt. Ballard	9/24/22	4:05	yes		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Mules, Mt. Ballard	10/12/22	2:49	yes		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Mules, Mt. Ballard	10/22/22	2:58	no		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Pinalenos	4/3/21	0:13	yes	yes (Dos Cabezas)	no	no
Pinalenos	8/28/21	0:20	yes	yes (Chiricahuas)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Pinalenos	6/5/22	0:20	yes	yes (Chiricahuas)	no	no
Quinlans	3/27/22	0:50	yes		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Quinlans	4/23/22	0:35	no	yes (Coyotes)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Quinlans	5/26/22	0:35	yes		yes	<i>U. ornatus</i>
Santa Ritas-Madera Creek*	5/15/21	0:50	no		yes	no
Santa Ritas-Madera Creek	5/31/21	1:45	yes		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>

Santa Ritas-Madera Creek	10/11/21	0:52	yes	no (Santa Ritas: Dutch John Trail)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Madera Creek	4/30/22	1:28	no	yes (Santa Ritas: Gardner Canyon, Mount Hopkins)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Madera Creek	6/2/22	1:22	no		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Madera Creek*	10/30/22	1:20	no		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Dutch John Trail*	10/11/21	0:21	no	yes (Santa Ritas: Madera Creek)	no	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Dutch John Trail*	10/29/21	2:00	no		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Dutch John Trail*	11/28/21	1:15	no		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Santa Ritas-Dutch John Trail	4/3/22	0:49	yes		yes	<i>S. clarkii</i>
Winchesters	10/16/21	1:54	no?		yes	<i>S. clarkii?</i>
Winchesters	3/15/22	3:16	no		yes	<i>U. ornatus</i>
Winchesters	4/16/22	3:46	yes	yes (Dragoons)	no	<i>U. ornatus</i>

193 **TABLE S3. Summary of approximate time spent searching on those transects with inferred**
 194 **local extinctions.** Each visit is the total number of resurveys of that transect. Searches are the
 195 number of searches of the specific site where *S. jarrovi* was recorded at the lowest elevation on that
 196 transect. For the second visit to the Baboquivaris, the lowest-elevation sites were surveyed both on
 197 the way up the transect and again on the way down (separate searches, same day). For the other
 198 transects, the distinction between searches of low-elevation sites on the way up and down the
 199 transect was not so discrete. For most transects, we give the amount of time spent specifically at or
 200 near the former lowest-elevation sites. In most cases (6/10), those sites encompassed a small area
 201 that could be searched fully in a limited amount of time. These included the Baboquivaris, Coyotes,
 202 Mules (Guest Road), Mules-1 (Juniper Flats), Pinalenos, and the Quinlans. In other cases (4/10), the
 203 transect was relatively lengthy (Mules-2, Santa Ritas-1, Santa Ritas-2, Winchesters). In these latter
 204 cases, the entire transect included potential habitat for *S. jarrovi* (i.e. Maderan evergreen woodland).
 205 For example, the Mules-2 transect begins at a higher elevation than the former low-elevation site in
 206 the Mules (Guest Road). Note that there are only 9 transects with inferred local extinctions, but the
 207 two Mules transects share the same lowest-elevation sites (Guest Road), and the surveys at this low-
 208 elevation location were counted separately. For the Winchesters, we show only the time spent
 209 specifically at the highest elevations (>1800 meters), although there are historical records for *S.*
 210 *jarrovi* at lower elevations on this transect. Full details are given in Appendix S1. Data on time are
 211 given in Dataset S1, and are taken from the time when a suitable rock outcrop without lizards was
 212 found (indicated as “0” in Dataset S1) or when lizards were first found at that site or transect
 213 (regardless of species), up until the last lizard sighting or lizard-free rock outcrop on the transect.
 214 Note that we do not give “person hours” for searching these transects. Although two people were
 215 present on most searches, the two people always searched the same part of the transect at the same
 216 time.
 217

Mountain range	Visits	Searches	Total time
Baboquivari	2	3	1:40
Coyotes	2	2	1:20
Mules (low elevation; Guest Road)	3	3	2:36
Mules-1 (Juniper Flat)	3	3	1:40
Mules-2 (Mount Ballard)	3	3	9:52
Pinalenos	3	3	0:53
Quinlans	3	3	2:00
Santa Ritas-1 (Madera Creek)	6	6	8:07
Santa Ritas-2 (Dutch John Springs)	4	4	4:25
Winchesters	3	3	4:47

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220 **TABLE S4. Summary of approximate time spent searching on transects without inferred local**
 221 **extinctions.** For all of these transects, *Sceloporus jarrovi* was found to be present in 2021–2022 at
 222 the same lowest elevation (or lower) than in the initial surveys (2013–2017). Each visit is the total
 223 number of resurveys of that transect. Searches are the number of searches of the specific site where
 224 *S. jarrovi* was recorded at the lowest elevation on that transect. For most transects, *S. jarrovi* was
 225 found on the first visit and the first search. The “time to first sighting” refers to the time between the
 226 start of the survey and when *S. jarrovi* was first recorded. For transects where *S. jarrovi* was only
 227 found on the second visit, we also give the time spent searching on the first visit (“Time on
 228 unsuccessful search”). For these two-visit transects, the “time to first sighting” refers to the second
 229 visit (the visit on which it was actually found). For several transects, the time to first sighting is
 230 given as 0, indicating that *S. jarrovi* was found immediately upon arriving at the relevant site (e.g. in
 231 the Dragoons, the lowest-elevation individual was spotted before we could exit the car). Full details
 232 are given in Appendix S1. Data on time are from Dataset S1, and are taken from when a potentially
 233 suitable rock outcrop lacking lizards was found (indicated as “0” in Dataset S1) or when a lizard was
 234 first found at that site (regardless of species), up until the last lizard sighting or lizard-free outcrop on
 235 the transect. Note that we do not give “person hours” for searching these transects. Although two
 236 people were present on most searches, the two people always searched the same part of the transect
 237 at the same time. The average time to the first sighting was 12 minutes. However, this only counts
 238 visits that were successful. If the unsuccessful searches for four transects are included, the average
 239 increases to 27 minutes.
 240

Mountain range	Visits	Searches	Time to first sighting	Time on unsuccessful search
Canelos	1	1	0:19	
Chiricahuas	1	1	0:00	
Dos Cabezas	1	1	0:00	
Dragoons	1	1	0:00	
Galiuros	1	2	0:19	0:10
Huachucas	1	1	0:16	
Little Dragoons	1	1	0:23	
Patagonias	2	2	0:18	1:00
Perillas	1	1	0:12	
Santa Ritas-3	2	2	0:00	0:52
Santa Teresas	2	2	0:11	1:00
Whetstones	1	1	0:27	

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243 **TABLE S5. Summary of approximate time spent searching at surviving sites sampled for**
 244 **genetic data.** Note that genetic data were obtained from a total of 27 populations (Table S10) and
 245 only 17 are listed here: the others are in Tables S3 and S4. Genetic data were also obtained from
 246 several lowest-elevation populations that went locally extinct (Baboquivaris, Coyotes, Mules [Guest
 247 Road], Winchesters) which are listed in Table S3 instead. Genetic data were also obtained from
 248 several lowest-elevation populations that survived (Canelo Hills, Galiuros, Perillas, Santa Teresas,
 249 Whetstones), which are listed in Table S4. The sites listed here are unique to the genetic data (but are
 250 close to the others in some cases). One site was unique to the genetic data and also went extinct
 251 (Santa Ritas-Supertrail), but was lumped with Santa Ritas-Madera Creek in many analyses. The
 252 numbering of sites for the Santa Ritas is different from that for the other transects (in Tables S3 and
 253 S4). Each visit is the total number of resurveys undertaken to find *S. jarrovi* at that site. For most
 254 transects, *S. jarrovi* was found on the first visit. The “time to first sighting” refers to the time
 255 between the start of the survey and when *S. jarrovi* was first recorded. For transects where *S.*
 256 *jarrovi* was only found on the second visit, we also give the time spent searching on the first visit
 257 (“Time on unsuccessful search”). For these transects, the “time to first sighting” refers to the second
 258 visit (the visit on which it was actually found). For several transects, the time to first sighting is
 259 given as 0, indicating that *S. jarrovi* was found immediately upon arriving at the relevant site.
 260 Further details are given in Appendix S4. Note that at the Carr Canyon site, *S. jarrovi* was found on
 261 the first visit at both lower and higher sites, but not within 100 meters of the original genetic site. In
 262 the Little Dragoons, no *S. jarrovi* (or other lizards) were found on the first visit, but this was in
 263 February, which is before their most active period. Data on time are from Dataset S1, and are taken
 264 from when a potentially suitable rock outcrop lacking lizards was found (indicated as “0” in Dataset
 265 S1) or when a lizard was first found at that site (regardless of species). Note that we do not give
 266 “person hours” for searching these transects. Although two people were present on most searches,
 267 the two people always searched the same part of the transect at the same time. The average time to
 268 the first sighting on successful searches was 5 minutes. If the unsuccessful searches are included, the
 269 average increases to 10 minutes per transect.
 270

Mountain range	Visits	Time to first sighting	Time on unsuccessful search
Chiricahuas1: Turkey Creek, Morse Canyon	1	0:00	
Chiricahuas2: Rucker Canyon	1	0:08	
Chiricahuas3: east slope Cave Creek Canyon	1	0:00	
Chiricahuas4: near Idlewild Campground	1	0:05	
Chiricahuas5: East Turkey Creek, Farm Road 42	1	0:00	
Dos Cabezas	1	0:10	
Dragoons1: Cochise Stronghold	1	0:23	
Dragoons2: China Peak Road	1	0:00	
Huachucas1: upper Scotia Canyon	1	0:03	
Huachucas2: Carr Canyon	2	0:06	0:29
Little Dragoons: near Amerind Museum	2	0:19	0:47
Patagonias1: west of crest (>1700 m)	1	0:08	
Patagonias2: east of crest (>1700 m)	1	0:04	
Pinalenos1: Route366, above Arcadia Camp	1	0:00	
Pinalenos2: Tripp Canyon	1	0:07	
Quinlans: near Kitt Peak	1	0:00	
Santa Ritas2: Mount Hopkins	1	0:00	

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TABLE S6. Elevational range shifts in *Sceloporus jarrovi* and *S. clarkii*. Initial elevations of the lower edge limits in *S. jarrovi* and upper edge limits in *S. clarkii* on 21 transects were estimated in the initial surveys (2013–2017). Resurveys were conducted in 2021 and 2022. Positive values for shifts and shift rates indicate upward elevational range shifts, whereas negative values indicate downward shifts. The Santa Ritas consisted of three transects: 1=Madera Creek, 2=Dutch John Spring Trail, 3=Gardner Canyon. The Mules included two: 1=Juniper Flats Road, 2=Escabrosa Ridge (Mount Ballard). Full survey data are in Dataset S1. Note that *S. clarkii* did not occur on all transects or was sometimes observed only in the first survey or only the resurvey; cases in which *S. clarkii* was not observed are indicated with “–”. *=transects where *S. jarrovi* was considered locally extinct at the initial (2013–2017) lowest elevation site after the resurveys in 2021–2022. Mountain ranges are listed alphabetically.

Transect	<i>Sceloporus jarrovi</i>					<i>Sceloporus clarkii</i>				
	Initial elevation (m)	Resurvey elevation (m)	Years between surveys	Shift (m)	Shift rate (m/year)	Initial elevation (m)	Resurvey elevation (m)	Years between surveys	Shift (m)	Shift rate (m/year)
Baboquivaris*	1836.42	1981.20	7	144.78	20.68	1795.58	1966.87	7	171.30	24.47
Canelo Hills	1665.73	1667.26	6	1.52	0.25	1656.59	–	–	–	–
Chiricahuas	1496.57	1490.47	7	-6.10	-0.87	1516.38	1511.81	6	-4.57	-0.76
Coyotes*	1588.62	1605.08	7	16.46	2.35	1586.48	1597.15	7	10.67	1.52
Dos Cabezas	1274.67	1259.43	6	-15.24	-2.54	–	–	–	–	–
Dragoons	1506.93	1489.56	8	-17.37	-2.17	1440.18	–	–	–	–
Galiuros	1654.45	1648.05	7	-6.40	-0.91	1546.25	–	–	–	–
Huachucas	1790.09	1776.07	6	-14.02	-2.34	1685.85	–	–	–	–
Little Dragoons	1429.21	1427.68	7	-1.52	-0.22	1450.85	1427.68	8	-23.16	-2.90
Mules 1*	1747.72	2162.56	7	414.83	59.26	1809.90	2058.92	7	249.02	35.57
Mules 2*	1747.72	2165.30	8	417.58	52.20	1809.90	1951.02	8	141.12	17.64
Patagonias	1682.80	1626.11	8	-56.69	-7.09	1652.02	–	–	–	–
Perillas	1833.37	1830.02	8	-3.00	-0.42	–	1848.92	–	–	–
Pinalenos*	1749.55	1840.99	6	91.44	15.24	1578.25	1748.94	6	170.69	28.45
Quinlans*	1480.72	1495.35	9	15.00	1.63	1416.10	1477.06	9	60.96	6.77
Santa Ritas 1*	1494.43	1628.24	4	133.81	33.45	1585.87	1662.68	9	76.81	8.53
Santa Ritas 2*	1542.29	1852.27	9	309.98	34.44	1550.82	1826.36	6	275.54	45.92
Santa Ritas 3	1819.66	1816.91	8	-2.74	-0.34	1818.13	–	–	–	–
Santa Teresas	1579.47	1584.96	6	5.49	0.91	1575.21	1602.03	6	26.82	4.47

Whetstones	2087.27	2092.15	7	4.88	0.70	1801.67	2076.91	7	275.23	39.32
Winchesters*	1866.90	1918.72	7	51.82	7.40	1864.46	–	–	–	–

TABLE S7. Historical records and elevational range shifts for *Sceloporus jarrovi*. Usable museum or literature records were found for the lowest-elevation site for *S. jarrovi* for 12 of the 21 recent transects for the period before the initial surveys (2013–2017): see Appendix S3 for details. For each transect, we give the year of the historical record (1956–2005), the recent year the transect was surveyed (2013–2017), the latitude, longitude, and elevational for the historical record, the recent lowest elevation from the initial survey (2013–2017), the shift in the lower elevational range limits between the recent and historical records (upwards positive, downwards negative), the rate of change in elevation (the shift divided by the number of years between surveys), the specific source for the GPS coordinates (i.e. given in the museum record or estimated from the locality given) and the reference for the historical record (almost all from museum specimen localities). Transects are listed in order of the largest upward shift to the largest downward shift. We did not include transects with no shifts or with downward shifts in our analyses (labeled “persistent” below) because it is possible that the lower elevation sites where the species was found in 2013–2017 were simply not surveyed (or collected at) in the period 1956–2005 (see Appendix S3). The Santa Ritas included three transects: 1=Madera Creek; 2=Dutch John Spring Trail, 3=Gardner Canyon. TR=Township and Range coordinates.

Transect	Historical year	Recent year	Historical latitude	Historical longitude	Historical elevation (m)	Recent elevation (m)	Shift (m)	Shift rate (m/year)	Source of coordinates	Reference
Whetstones	1997	2015	31.7714	-110.4167	1700.78	2087.27	386.49	21.47	as in record, lowest elevation chosen	Turner et al. (2003)
Galiuros	2000	2014	32.6562	-110.2810	1449.93	1654.45	204.52	14.61	as in record	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-52117
Winchesters	1999	2015	32.3132	-110.0835	1670.30	1866.90	196.60	12.29	TR coordinates converted, estimated	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-51868
Santa Ritas 3	1967	2014	31.7244	-110.7481	1569.72	1819.66	249.94	5.32	TR coordinates converted, estimated	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-19874
Pinalenos	1958	2015	32.6688	-109.7888	1615.44	1749.55	134.11	2.35	estimated	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-02613
Canelo Hills	2005	2015	31.4368	-110.4547	1642.87	1665.73	22.86	2.29	estimated	http://arctos.database.museum/guid/UTEP:Herp:18492

Quinlans	1962	2013	31.9773	-111.6032	1463.04	1480.72	17.68	0.35	estimated	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-04586
Dragoons	1969	2013	31.9215	-109.9664	1506.93	1506.93	0.00	persistent (0.00)	estimated	http://arctos.database.museum/guid/UCM:Herp:40865
Chiricahuas	1956	2015	31.8917	-109.1658	1524.00	1496.57	-27.43	persistent (-0.46)	as in record	http://arctos.database.museum/guid/MVZ:Herp:67095
Santa Ritas-1	1970	2017	31.7218	-110.8804	1524.00	1494.43	-29.57	persistent (-0.63)	estimated	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-32094
Santa Teresas	1973	2015	32.8573	-110.2196	1734.62	1579.47	-155.14	persistent (-3.69)	as in record	http://portal.vertnet.org/o/uaz/herpetology?id=urn-catalog-uaz-herpetology-uaz-35750
Santa Ritas-2	1996	2013	31.7214	-110.8625	1645.92	1542.29	-103.63	persistent (-6.10)	as in record	http://arctos.database.museum/guid/MVZ:Herp:225543

TABLE S8. Correlations among climatic variables at the lowest-elevation range edges. Climatic variables are based on the time of the initial survey (mean of 2 years prior) at the lowest-elevation site for each transect. Results are based on Pearson correlation in R. Data for each site are in Dataset S3. *P*-values <0.05 are boldfaced. The climatic variables are: MAT=mean annual temperature, in °C; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in °C; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DD0=degree-days below 0°C, in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm.

Variable 1	Variable 2	<i>r</i>	<i>P</i>
MAT	MWMT	0.9624	1.23E-11
MAT	MAP	-0.0770	0.7468
MAT	DD_0	-0.9515	1.17E-10
MAT	CMD	0.2857	0.2220
MWMT	MAP	-0.1964	0.4066
MWMT	DD_0	-0.8614	1.07E-06
MWMT	CMD	0.2999	0.1990
MAP	DD_0	-0.1065	0.6549
MAP	CMD	-0.7948	2.83E-05
DD_0	CMD	-0.1488	0.5311

TABLE S9. Correlations in levels of climate change between surveys among climatic variables at the lowest-elevation range edges. Climatic variables are based on the change in each variable between surveys. Results are based on Pearson correlation in R. Data for each site are in Dataset S3. *P*-values <0.05 are boldfaced. The climatic variables are: MAT=mean annual temperature, in °C; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in °C; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DD0=degree-days below 0°C, in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm.

Variable 1	Variable 2	<i>r</i>	<i>P</i>
MAT	MWMT	0.3255	0.1613
MAT	MAP	0.0059	0.9802
MAT	DD_0	-0.5429	0.0134
MAT	CMD	0.0995	0.6765
MWMT	MAP	0.0799	0.7379
MWMT	DD_0	-0.0314	0.8955
MWMT	CMD	-0.1349	0.5707
MAP	DD_0	-0.5495	0.0121
MAP	CMD	-0.8656	<0.0001
DD_0	CMD	0.6279	0.0030

TABLE S10. Overview of sites from which genetic data were obtained for *Sceloporus jarrovi*.

Note that numbering of locations for genetic data for the Santa Ritas is not identical to that for the other transects (Tables S2–S3). Genetic material was collected from 27 sites across 18 mountain ranges during recent surveys (2014–2015) and earlier sampling (1996–2001). Sample elevation is in meters above sea level. For samples collected along an elevational transect, the lowest elevation is given. In the resurveys in 2021 and 2022, the population status was classified as persistent when at least one individual of *S. jarrovi* was recorded at the sample site (within ~100 m and at equivalent or lower elevations), or if it was found farther away but nearby (110–860 meters distance) at lower elevations (see Appendix S4). If no individuals were found in the resurveys, the site was classified as extinct. Asterisks (*) indicate lowest-edge populations. Populations indicated with “^x” were excluded from analyses of genetic variation (π) because genetic data were obtained from only one individual. Under “Status” populations indicated with an “^o” were considered as persistent in an alternative analysis. Specifically, the Santa Rita locality for genetic data near the Super Trail is entirely extinct, but a nearby population persists in Madera Creek. In the Winchesters, the population at the lowest-elevation sites appears to have gone extinct but the population at nearby higher elevation sites is still persistent. We performed alternative analyses treating these two populations as either extinct or persistent.

Genetic sample site	Collection years	Latitude	Longitude	Sample elevation (m)	Population status
Baboquivaris*	2015	31.77217	-111.58957	1836.42	extinct
Canelo Hills*	2015	31.44320	-110.44818	1665.73	persistent
Chiricahuas 1 (Turkey Creek)	2014	31.84456	-109.32384	2072.00	persistent
Chiricahuas 2 (Rucker Canyon Road)	2015	31.76670	-109.32613	1788.57	persistent
Chiricahuas 3* (Cave Creek Canyon)	2015	31.89962	-109.15857	1496.57	persistent
Chiricahuas 4 (Idlewild Camp)	2015	31.89055	-109.16920	1534.06	persistent
Chiricahuas 5 (East Turkey Creek)	1996–2001	31.90909	-109.25195	1957.12	persistent
Coyotes*	2015	31.99590	-111.54185	1588.62	extinct
Dos Cabezas*	2015	32.23168	-109.49518	1304.54	persistent
Dragoons 1 (Cochise Stronghold)	2015	31.91102	-109.96448	1578.56	persistent
Dragoons 2 (China Peak Road)	1998	31.89445	-109.98023	1980.90	persistent
Galiuros*	2014	32.65338	-110.28510	1654.45	persistent
Huachucas 1 (Scotia Canyon)	2014	31.46137	-110.39212	1887.32	persistent
Huachucas 2 (Carr Canyon)	1998–2001	31.43325	-110.28077	2028.75	persistent
Little Dragoons*	2014–2015	32.04527	-110.08195	1449.63	persistent
Mules*	2014	31.46017	-109.95323	1747.72	extinct
Patagonias 1 ^x (West Duquesne Road)	2015	31.38762	-110.71743	1773.33	persistent
Patagonias 2 (East Duquesne Road)	1998	31.38810	-110.70309	1777.90	persistent
Perillas* ^x	2014	31.46490	-109.42582	1833.37	persistent
Pinalenos 1 (State Route 366)	1998	32.64167	-109.82049	2140.92	persistent
Pinalenos 2 (Tripp Canyon)	1998	32.76257	-110.07000	1894.94	persistent
Quinlans	1998	31.95454	-111.61305	1920.85	persistent
Santa Ritas 1* (Super Trail)	2014	31.71293	-110.87283	1670.30	extinct ^o
Santa Ritas 2 (Mt Hopkins Road)	1997	31.67440	-110.87947	2147.93	persistent
Santa Teresas*	2015	32.84755	-110.19627	1586.18	persistent
Whetstones*	2015	31.76975	-110.43533	2087.27	persistent
Winchesters*	2015	32.32217	-110.08205	1866.90	extinct ^o

TABLE S11. Results of logistic regression models of initial elevation, climate, and warm-edge extinction. The initial elevation and climate at the lowest-elevation site on each transect (average of two years before the first survey at each site, 2013–2017) was tested as a predictor of current (2021–2022) population status at these sites (extinct vs. persistent; the model predicts persistence). A total of 20 sites (one per transect) were included, with just one lowest-elevation site for the Mules (shared by the Mules-1 and Mules-2 transects). The five climate variables were: MAT=mean annual temperature, in °C; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in °C; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DD0=degree-days below 0°C, in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm. Climate data are in Dataset S3. Note that MAP and CMD were both significant predictors of local extinction, but local extinction was associated with higher MAP (indicating more initial precipitation in populations that went extinct) and lower CMD (indicating greater initial climatic moisture in populations that went extinct).

Response	Environmental variable	Coefficient estimate	Std. Error	<i>p</i>-value
Population status	Elevation	-0.001	0.002	0.890
Population status	MAT	-0.404	0.446	0.353
Population status	MWMT	-0.306	0.403	0.442
Population status	MAP	-0.009	0.005	0.041
Population status	DD0	0.041	0.046	0.350
Population status	CMD	0.009	0.005	0.016

TABLE S12. Results of logistic regression models of final climate and warm-edge extinction.

The current climate at the lowest-elevation site on each transect (average of 2 years before the first resurvey at each site, 2021–2022) was tested as a predictor of current population status at these sites (extinct vs. persistent; the model predicts persistence). A total of 20 sites (one per transect) were included, with just one lowest-elevation site for the Mules (shared by the Mules-1 and Mules-2 transects). The five climate variables were: MAT=mean annual temperature, in °C; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in °C; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DD0=degree-days below 0°C, in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm. Climate data are in Dataset S3. Note that CMD was a significant predictor of local extinction, but local extinction was associated with lower CMD (indicating greater climatic moisture in populations that went extinct)

Response	Environmental variable	Coefficient estimate	Std. Error	<i>p</i>-value
Population status	MAT	-0.479	0.430	0.248
Population status	MWMT	-0.283	0.355	0.418
Population status	MAP	-0.009	0.006	0.088
Population status	DD0	0.035	0.042	0.387
Population status	CMD	0.011	0.007	0.041

TABLE S13. Results of logistic regression models of climate change and lowest-edge extinction.

Total climate change between surveys and rates of climate change between surveys were tested as predictors for population status (extinct vs. persistent; the model predicts persistence) for the lowest-elevation site on each transect ($n=20$ sites). A total of 20 sites (one per transect) were included, with just one lowest-elevation site for the Mules (the lowest-elevation site is shared by the two transects, Mules-1 and Mules-2). The five climate variables were: MAT=mean annual temperature, in °C; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in °C; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DD0=degree-days below 0°C, in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm. Climate data are in Dataset S3. The results indicate that local extinction is associated with larger increases in MAT and higher rates of change in MAT.

Climatic variable	Total climate change			Rate of climate change		
	Coefficient estimate	Std. error	<i>p</i> -value	Coefficient estimate	Std. error	<i>p</i> -value
MAT	-8.065	4.539	0.029	-52.158	30.238	0.045
MWMT	-0.721	1.389	0.598	-10.996	22.248	0.616
MAP	0.007	0.007	0.309	0.164	0.171	0.318
DD0	0.007	0.156	0.962	41.979	90.010	0.639
CMD	-0.010	0.007	0.108	-0.331	0.237	0.083

TABLE S14. Results of logistic regression analyses testing whether genetic variation predicts local extinction. Levels of genetic variation within populations (π =nucleotide diversity) were tested as predictors for population status (extinct vs. persistent; the model predicts survival). Analyses were done including samples obtained in 2014–2015 and 1996–2001 ($n=25$ populations; Dataset S5), and also on only those obtained in 2014–2015 ($n=16$ populations; Dataset S6). The results indicate that surviving populations have higher levels of genetic variation. Note that for the analyses of 16 populations, there is only a single population per mountain range (except for the Chiricahuas, with 4 populations, all persistent).

Response	Populations (<i>n</i>)	Genetic variable	Coefficient estimate	Std. error	<i>p</i>-value
Population status	25	π	15134.523	6993.498	0.004
Population status	16	π	11762.518	6639.130	0.026

TABLE S15. Results of logistic regression analyses testing whether genetic variation predicts extinction of lowest-edge populations. Levels of genetic variation within populations (π =nucleotide diversity) from the lowest-edge populations ($n=12$; all with >1 individuals) was tested as a predictor of population status (extinct vs. persistent; the model predicts survival). Analyses were done including samples obtained in both periods (2014–2015 and 1996–2001; Dataset S5). In an alternative analysis, two populations with extinction at some sites (Santa Ritas-1, Winchesters) were classified as persistent (Appendix S4). The results indicate that surviving populations have higher levels of genetic variation. The main analyses (Table S14) included all 25 populations, not just lowest-edge populations. Note that when including only lowest-edge populations, there is only one population per mountain range.

Response	Analysis	Coefficient estimate	Std. error	<i>p</i>-value
Population status	main	10065.612	6908.111	0.086
Population status	alternative	17135.351	11018.277	0.036

TABLE S16. Results of multiple regression analyses of local extinction. Logistic regression with binomial generalized linear models (glm) were used, with data from the 11 low-elevation populations having genetic data (and >1 individual sampled per population). When including only lowest-edge populations, there is only one population per mountain range. One value (Whetstones) was removed since this population was previously identified as outlier in the genetic variation analysis (Fig. 3B; but was also the highest-elevation site, see Fig. 1). The response variable was population status (extinct vs. persistent). Model 4 included an interaction term (*) between the two variables, and had the lowest AIC value (best fit). cMAT=change in mean annual temperature between surveys, in °C; π =nucleotide diversity. Model 1=cMAT only; Model 2= π only; Model 3=cMAT + π (multiple regression model with both predictor variables); Model 4=cMAT * π (multiple regression model with both predictor variables and an interaction term). Note that removal of the outlier population (Whetstones) is not problematic for our conclusions, even though the site in the Whetstones had very low genetic variation and survived recent climate change. The current lowest-elevation site in the Whetstones is at a very high elevation and is the coolest low-elevation site among these transects (Fig. S6; Dataset S3). Therefore, it would be the least likely populations to need high genetic variation to survive very recent climate change (note that these analyses here do not consider current climate, only the amount of climate change). Furthermore, the populations in the Whetstones suffered the most dramatic range shift among historical populations (Fig. S1), consistent with the pattern of low genetic variation.

Model	Variables	Estimate	Std. error	<i>p</i> -value	AIC
1	cMAT	-4.618	4.785	0.302	18.092
2	π	27709.398	17222.013	0.006	11.736
3	cMAT	3.233	11.174	0.769	13.649
3	π	31787.395	25076.556	0.011	
4	cMAT	-1.549e+04	3.583e+06	0.769	8.000
4	π	2.613e+06	5.940e+08	0.011	
4	cMAT * π	6.532e+07	1.505e+10	0.006	

TABLE S17. Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) strongly associated with climatic variables. Results are from correlation analyses (Fig. S5) of each climatic variable and genetic data from the full genomic dataset (all 115 individuals, Dataset S5), using latent-factor mixed models (LFMM). GIF=Genomic Inflation Factor. Adjusted GIF corresponds to the GIF used for the final model. The number of total candidate SNPs per climate variable and identity (i.e. position within the aligned nucleotide sequence) of the top three candidates (lowest p -value) are indicated. A total of 8 SNPs were identified as being in the top three among all five climatic variables. The five climatic variables tested were: MAT=mean annual temperature, in °C; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature, in °C; MAP=mean annual precipitation, in mm; DD0=degree-days below 0°C, in days; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit, in mm.

Variable	Default GIF	Adjusted GIF	Number of SNPs in total	Top 1	Top 2	Top 3
MAT	1.09	1.18	20	224233	285591	156479
MWMT	1.19	1.35	15	224233	285591	156479
MAP	1.51	1.52	10	224233	285591	224005
DD0	0.91	0.91	43	40569	421414	404828
CMD	1.56	1.56	24	224233	285591	62550

TABLE S18. Candidate genes identified in latent factor mixed models. The top three candidate SNPs associated with the five climatic variables are listed (8 unique candidate SNPs in total; Table S17). The corresponding gene is listed for each SNP, if it is located within an annotated gene. The species with the annotated genome that was used is listed here (*Anolis*=*Anolis carolinensis*, *Podarcis*=*Podarcis muralis*, *Mus*=*Mus musculus*). "No annotation" indicates that no information on the amino-acid sequence was available. Protein names and functions were extracted from the UniProt database. "Non-synonymous" indicates if a change in the candidate SNP would induce a non-synonymous change in the amino acid sequence, and which part of the protein would be affected. The five climate variables tested were: MAT=mean annual temperature; MWMT=mean warmest month temperature; MAP=mean annual precipitation; DD0=degree-days below 0°C; and CMD=Hargreaves climatic moisture deficit.

SNP	Non-synonymous	Correlated variables	Gene (Organism)	Protein	Key functions (extracted from UniProt)	Source (UniProt)
224233	no annotation	MAT, MWMT, MAP, CMD	Tlr13 (<i>Podarcis</i>)	Toll-like receptor 13	innate and adaptive immunity, inflammatory responses	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprotkb/A0670ILA0
285591	yes, protein-coding	MAT, MWMT, MAP, DD0, CMD	KRIT1 (<i>Anolis</i>)	FERM domain-containing protein	cell redox homeostasis, positive regulation of protein binding, negative regulation of angiogenesis	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/G1KRC6
156479	no annotation	MAT, MWMT, DD0, CMD	uncharacterized LOC121914887	--	--	
224005	no annotation	MAT, MWMT, MAP, DD0, CMD	LMTK2 (<i>Anolis</i>)	Protein kinase domain-containing protein	ATP binding, axonogenesis, regulation of kinase activity	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/H9GIT2
40569	yes, protein-coding	MAT, MWMT, DD0	KIF13B (<i>Podarcis</i>)	Kinesin family member 13B	ATP binding, microtubule binding and movement	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/A0A670HTP2
421414	no annotation	MAT, MWMT, DD0	FNDC3A (<i>Mus</i>)	Fibronectin type-III domain-containing protein 3A	cell-cell adhesion, fertilization (in mouse, not characterised in <i>Anolis</i> /wall lizard)	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/Q8BX90
404828	yes, protein-coding	MAT, MWMT, DD0, CMD	FBN2 (<i>Anolis</i>)	Fibrillin 2	calcium ion binding, extracellular matrix structural constituent, peptidase activity, regulation of body fluid levels	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/G1KAM9
62550	no annotation	MAT, MWMT, CMD	EXPH5 (<i>Anolis</i>)	Exophilin 5	small GTPase binding, intracellular protein transport	https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/A0A803TRK1

TABLE S19. NCBI accession numbers and sequences for candidate SNPs. Sequence fragments were used with the BLASTN algorithm in NCBI (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) to identify the position of the top candidate single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within the reference genome for *Sceloporus undulatus*. Candidate SNPs are in bold and underlined. NCBI accession code for the reference which gave the lowest E-value (best fit of the query sequence to the reference).

SNP	E-value	NCBI reference	Query sequence
224233	0.660	XM_042475485.1	AATCCCAC <u>CC</u> CAGTGGGGTTT
285591	0.660	XM_042475871.1	CAGCTATGGGAAT <u>T</u> ATGACA
156479	0.660	XR_006100600.1	CTATACCAA <u>A</u> CTACCTTCCC
224005	0.170	XM_042437551.1	AATGGGGC <u>CT</u> GAGCATAGGC
40569	0.170	XM_042445255.1	AGGTCG <u>G</u> TCTCAGAGAAGTT
421414	0.660	XM_042479779.1	TACACGCAT <u>T</u> TCCATTTTTG
404828	2.600	XM_042447774.1	CACC <u>C</u> CCCCAGGGTAACACT
62550	0.011	XM_042459092.1	GGG <u>G</u> GGCAAACCTGCAGCCTT

TABLE S20. Frequencies of candidate SNP bases in each population. The top three candidate SNPs associated with climatic variables (8 unique candidate SNPs in total; Tables S17–S19) and their nucleotide bases frequencies are shown within each population. Each population sampled for genetic data is listed. Currently extinct populations are indicated with “°”. The lowest-edge populations in each mountain range (with genetic data) are marked with asterisks (others were sampled at higher elevations than their lowest limit). The number of individuals with genetic data in each population is given. The first column for each SNP shows the most common base for that nucleotide position (across all populations) whereas the second column shows the less common variant (if present). The number of individuals with missing data is given as a superscript adjacent to the base frequency. In all these cases, data are missing because data are missing for the locus entirely (as expected from RADseq data), and not because of length variation within the locus. Note that climate-related SNPs could be associated with hotter or colder climates (for temperature variables), or wetter or drier climates (for precipitation variables).

Population	Base frequency (%) within 8 candidate SNPs																
	Number of individuals	SNP 224233		SNP 285591		SNP 404828		SNP 156479		SNP 224005		SNP 40569		SNP 421414		SNP 62550	
		C	T	T	A	C	T	A	C	C	T	G	A	T	A	G	A
Baboquivaris*°	6	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ³		
Canelo Hills*	2	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ¹		
Chiricahuas 1	2	100	100	100	100	100	75	25	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ¹		
Chiricahuas 2	5	100	100	100 ³	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ²		
Chiricahuas 3*	3	100 ¹	100	100 ¹	100	100	83.3	16.7	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ¹		
Chiricahuas 4	2	100	100 ¹	100 ¹	100 ¹	50	50	50	50	100 ¹							
Chiricahuas 5	6	100	83.3	16.7	66.7	33.3	91.7	8.3	75	25	100	100	100	100	100		
Coyotes*°	2	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Dos Cabezas*	4	100	100	100	100	12.5	87.5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Dragoons 1	2	100	100 ¹	100 ¹	100 ¹	100	100 ¹	100	100 ¹	100	100 ¹	100 ¹	100 ¹	100 ¹	100		
Dragoons 2	6	100	100 ¹	100 ¹	100 ¹	100	100	100 ⁴	100	100	100	100	100	83.3	16.7		
Galiuros*	7	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	78.6	21.4		
Huachucas 1	5	100	100 ¹	100 ³	100	100	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100 ³			
Huachucas 2	7	100 ¹	100 ¹	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Little Dragoons*	4	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Mules*°	5	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ²		
Patagonias 1	1	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Patagonias 2	2	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Perillas*	1	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Pinalenos 1	5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Pinalenos 2	8	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	75	25	68.8	31.2	100 ¹	100 ¹			
Quinlans	8	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	93.8	6.2	100 ¹	100 ¹			
Santa Ritas 1*°	7	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ²		
Santa Ritas 2	3	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Santa Teresas*	4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Whetstones*	2	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
Winchesters*°	6	100	100	100 ¹	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100 ²		

Captions for Datasets S1–S9

Dataset S1. Field survey data

Dataset S2. Literature dataset on range shifts

Dataset S3. Climate data for lowest-elevation sites

Dataset S4. RADseq sample locations

Dataset S5. RADseq data for all 115 individuals

Dataset S6. RADseq data for 70 recent individuals

Dataset S7. Genetic variation within populations

Dataset S8. Climate data for LFMM analyses

Dataset S9. Code and scripts for statistical analyses

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